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Executive summary

This report summarises the final conference of the TIMEPAC project, titled [“Innovating Energy Certification: Transforming Building Performance Assessment”](#), which was held at the Catalan Institute for Energy in Barcelona, Spain, on October 4, 2024.

The purpose of the conference was to present the results of the TIMEPAC project to relevant stakeholders, engage guest speakers on key issues identified throughout the project, and provide a platform for researchers and practitioners to share and discuss their experiences regarding the current state of building energy certification and ways to enhance it in line with the latest recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

The conference programme was organised into two main segments:

- Three roundtable discussions with experts in building performance certification, moderated by TIMEPAC partners.
- A paper session for external researchers to present and discuss their work, focusing on two key topics: enhanced energy performance certification and renovation passport.

This document includes the conference programme, a summary of the roundtable discussions, and the presented papers.

Presentations from the roundtables and papers can be accessed on the [project’s website](#), and a full recording of the conference is available in [video](#) format.

1 Introduction

The overall objective of the [TIMEPAC project, “Towards Innovative Methods for Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of Buildings,”](#) is to foster the implementation of a more holistic approach to energy certification by considering:

- The entire lifecycle of EPC-related data, from generation and storage to analysis and exploitation, covering the building’s design, construction, and operation stages.
- The recognition that buildings are part of a larger ecosystem, which includes energy and transport networks as well as the built environment.
- The dynamic nature of buildings, which continuously evolve over time.

TIMEPAC workshops play a vital role in the project’s communication and dissemination strategy. The TIMEPAC series began in [Barcelona](#) in 2019 and has since included three additional workshops in [Ljubljana](#) (2021), [Torino](#) (2022), and [Vienna](#) (2023).

The final conference for TIMEPAC took place on October 4, 2024, at the Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN) in [Barcelona](#), with approximately 75 attendees gathered in the main auditorium. The event brought together a diverse group, including TIMEPAC partners, guest speakers, researchers, and members of the public, creating an enriching environment for knowledge exchange.

The objective of the TIMEPAC workshops and conference has been to provide a platform for energy efficiency experts, researchers, and those interested in sustainability in the building sector to present and exchange their experiences, research progress, and results. The events also served as a forum to discuss the state of the art and determine future directions and priorities in the areas of building energy performance. This includes improving and disseminating knowledge on methods and tools for energy performance assessment, policies to promote deep building renovation, and technologies for enhancing energy efficiency in the building sector, in economic, environmental, and social terms.

The Barcelona conference also served as a collaborative platform for discussing advancements in energy certification processes and presenting recent research and developments aligned with the latest recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). Hosting the event at ICAEN underscored TIMEPAC’s mission to advance energy certification through collaborative efforts among all stakeholders, in alignment with the recast of the EPBD.

2 Conference dissemination

The conference was advertised at the [project website](#) and through the communication team through the social media channels of TIMEPAC (Figures 1-3).

Figure 1. Dissemination on the project website

Figure 2. Dissemination on LinkedIn

Figure 3. Dissemination on X

3 Conference programme

The purpose of the final conference was to share with relevant stakeholders the results of the TIMEPAC project, discuss with guest speakers the most critical issues identified in the project, and provide a space for researchers working on the fields of energy performance certification to present and discuss their results.

The programme was structured in two main blocks:

- three round tables with guest experts in the field of building performance certification, moderated by TIMEPAC partners
- a paper session for external researchers to present and discuss their work focusing on two main topics: enhanced energy performance certification and renovation passport

The round tables were focused on three topics:

Round table 1: Building renovation plans and passport

The role of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), as proposed by the latest recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), was examined in terms of its potential to accelerate the renovation of building stock, especially residential buildings. Speakers discussed the challenges of implementing renovation passports at national and European levels, addressing topics such as the assessment of building stock, securing financial investments, and developing new professional services.

Round table 2: Enhanced energy performance certificate

A key focus was the complementarity of EPCs with other certification schemes, particularly the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI). The conversation explored how building certificates could evolve into tools for continuous performance assessment within the broader sustainability context. Participants also considered the integration of these certifications and their potential to drive improvements in energy performance, as well as how operational data could enhance EPCs to make them more effective over time.

Round table 3: Improving building assessment through data integration

Building Information Modelling (BIM) was highlighted as a tool for gathering information from multiple sources throughout a building's lifetime, from design to operation. Discussions centred on how digital logbooks, BIM, and renovation passports could work together to manage and maintain building data throughout its lifecycle. The challenges of integrating EPC data with data from various sources were addressed, along with how these efforts support the vision for EPCs outlined in the EPBD.

The paper sessions included eight presentations, which had been previously selected by the scientific committee. Participants came from Austria, Greece, Italy, and Spain.

Agenda

9:00	Welcome and reception
9:30	Introduction - Leandro Madrazo, Project Coordinator
9:45	Opening - Lluís Morer, Head of Energy Efficiency at ICAEN
10:00	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive - Pau Garcia Audi, Policy Officer, Directory-General for Energy Efficiency, European Commission
Round tables	
11:00	<p>Round table 1: Building renovation plans and passport</p> <p>Moderation: Ainhoa Mata - ICAEN, Spain</p> <p>Speakers: Rui Fragoso - Head of Buildings and Efficiency of Resources at ADENE - Agência para a Energia, Portugal Silvio De Nigris - Public Officer at the Sustainable Energy Department, Regione Piemonte, Italy Killian Paenen - Product Owner of Woningpas/Gebouwenpas at the Flemish Energy and Climate Agency (VEKA), Flanders, Belgium</p>
12:00	<p>Round table 2: Enhanced energy performance certificate</p> <p>Moderation: Vincenzo Corrado - Politecnico di Torino, Italy</p> <p>Speakers: Licinio Alfaro - Head of Department of Sustainable Construction at ITeC, Spain Francesca Pagliaro - Researcher at ENEA, Italy Boris Sučić - Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia</p>
13:00	Lunch
14:00	<p>Round table 3: Improving building assessment through data integration</p> <p>Moderation: Álvaro Sicilia - La Salle- Ramon Llull University, Spain</p> <p>Speakers: Thomas Bednar - Head of Department at TU Wien, Austria Rolando Biere - Polytechnic University of Catalonia, Spain Gloria Calleja - CEMOSA, Spain</p>
Session 1: Enhanced EPC	
15:15	<p>Local Levelised Cost of Energy: Enhancing the SRI and EPC with financial indicators</p> <p>Rolf Bastiaanssen - Bax & Company, Barcelona, Spain</p>

15:30	<p>Towards seamless data integration through an open data model Sabine Sint, Galina Paskaleva, Thomas Bednar - TU Wien, Vienna, Austria</p>
15:45	<p>Configurations and qualities of new office building in Barcelona to meet current and new regulatory requirements Pablo González, Luca Volpi, Aurora Moyano, Hedda Egerlid - Societat Orgànica, Barcelona, Spain</p>
16:00	<p>Questions and answers</p>
16:15	<p>Coffee break</p>
<p>Session 2: Renovation Passport</p>	
16:30	<p>Towards sustainable construction for deep renovation: a comprehensive analysis of the transition from cost-optimal methodology to multi-objective methodology David Masip, Eva Crespo - Department of Architectural Technology, Barcelona School of Architecture (ETSAB) - BarcelonaTech Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain</p>
16:45	<p>iBRoad2EPC: Simplified renovation passport Eulàlia Figuerola, Alicia de la Fuente - Green Building Council España, Madrid, Spain</p>
17:00	<p>Integrating Renovation Passport Elements to the Greek Energy Performance Certificate: The Benaki Museum case study Eleftheria Touloupaki - Lab. of Building Construction and Physics, Dpt. of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece Charikleia Karakosta - Dpt. of Business Administration, University of Macedonia, Thessaloniki, Greece Alice Corovessi - INZEB, Athens, Greece</p>
17:15	<p>The facilitation service for energy renovation of public buildings in Piemonte Region Silvio De Nigris - Piemonte Region, Sustainable Energy Department, Turin, Italy Stefano Dotta - Environment Park SpA, Green Building Department, Turin, Italy</p>
17:30	<p>Spanish e-building logbook: Theoretical structure based on stakeholders' views. Paúl Espinoza, Carlos Marmolejo, Rolando Biere - Centre for Land Policy and Valuations, Barcelona School of Architecture (ETSAB) - BarcelonaTech Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain</p>
17:45	<p>Questions and answers</p>
18:00	<p>Concluding remarks</p>

4 Round tables

Round table 1 - Building renovation plans and passport

Figure 4. Participants in round table, from left to right: Ainhoa Mata, Silvio De Nigris, Rui Fragoso and Killian Paenen

Moderation:

Ainhoa Mata - ICAEN, Spain

Speakers:

Rui Fragoso - Head of Buildings and Efficiency of Resources, ADENE Agência para a Energia, Portugal

Silvio De Nigris - Public Officer at the Sustainable Energy Department, Regione Piemonte, Italy

Killian Paenen - Product Owner of Woningpas/Gebouwenpas at the Flemish Energy and Climate Agency (VEKA), Flanders, Belgium

Before beginning the discussion, Ainhoa Mata provided a summary of TIMEPAC's findings, emphasizing the integration of EPC and BIM to enhance and optimise the application of Renovation Passports. The presentation concluded with the following questions posed to the speakers for discussion:

- What are your perspectives on the Renovation Passport, and what challenges might arise during its implementation?
- What is the added value and role of the Renovation Passport in supporting retrofitting policies?
- How should the Renovation Passport be structured to help increase the renovation rate?
- Would it be advantageous to include additional indicators in the renovation scenario planning tool?
- Which specific projects are you involved in that relate to the Renovation Passport?

Following the presentation, round table participants engaged in a discussion summarised by the following key points:

Role and value of Renovation Passports

- Renovation Passports (RPs) are viewed as essential tools for driving building renovations by providing homeowners with a clear roadmap for improving their building's energy efficiency. They offer a more comprehensive and personalised approach than traditional EPCs.
- Unlike EPCs, RPs are fine-tuned for that specific homeowner at that specific building.
- They would need to incorporate graphical representations of road maps and sequence of recommendations to make them easily understandable to homeowners.
- The integration of technical and financial aspects is key to helping homeowners understand the costs and financing options associated with different renovation measures.
- Understanding the proper sequence of renovation steps is essential to keep options open for later stages of improvement, preventing potential obstacles caused by poorly planned initial actions.
- RPs could significantly support public financing schemes and green financing initiatives by providing structured, credible information on energy-efficient upgrades, as banks are increasingly attuned to aspects of the energy transition, which they can help to document and validate.
- Through systematic data collection on building renovations, RPs can offer policymakers valuable insights to design and assess retrofitting policies effectively. They can help to review not only the current condition of buildings but also how they evolve over time, supporting more informed and dynamic policy development.

Data repositories and integration

- Ensuring that the data in RPs is accurate and comprehensive is essential
- It is important to provide building robust data repositories that can collect, store, and share building information is highlighted.
- Effective data integration across different platforms and agencies is crucial for providing a comprehensive and user-friendly renovation passport.

Implementation challenges

- Differences in building regulations, definitions, and data formats across regions and municipalities pose challenges for data exchange and passport usability. For instance, in Flanders there is still not an agreed definition of “building unit”
- Accounting for unauthorised building modifications adds complexity to data collection and passport accuracy. Sometimes people build a student dwelling at the top floor of their house and they expect to get a building passport for that.
- Educating homeowners about the benefits and use of renovation passports is crucial for successful adoption.
- Keeping the cost of developing and issuing passports reasonable is important to ensure accessibility for all homeowners.

Voluntary vs. mandatory implementation

- While the European Union provides a framework for creating RPs, their implementation and whether they will be voluntary or mandatory are left to Member States to decide.
- Although the creation of RPs is voluntary, it is up to Member States to decide to make mandatory.

- Linking renovation passports to financial incentives or making them compulsory for certain building types could encourage wider adoption.
- RP could initially be required for less efficient, non-residential buildings as a way to encourage energy-saving measures. This requirement would incentivise these buildings to reduce energy consumption by following a structured, trackable renovation plan.

Generic vs. specific recommendations

- Participants emphasised the importance of learning from past experiences EPCs to ensure that RPs do not provide generic recommendations. Rather, they should be tailored to each context, serving as a balanced point of discussion between experts and homeowners. This would ensure that the advice given is relevant and specific to each building's unique needs, rather than relying on one-size-fits-all solutions that may not be effective in practice.
- Engaging homeowners and other stakeholders (installers, financial institutions, policymakers) in the development process is crucial to ensure the passports are tailored to specific needs and contexts.
- There is a recognised need for stakeholder engagement in the development of RPs. This input will help ensure that they are effective and consider the perspectives of all relevant parties affected by these changes.

In conclusion, by offering tailored, detailed roadmaps that integrate technical, financial, and sequential renovation strategies, RPs can address the limitations of traditional EPCs and empower homeowners to make informed decisions. Their potential to enhance policy design, support green financing, and improve data-driven planning underscores their value to both individuals and institutions. However, their successful implementation depends on overcoming challenges such as regulatory inconsistencies, data integration, cost management, and homeowner education. Engaging stakeholders throughout the development and adoption process will be crucial to ensuring RPs meet diverse needs effectively. Whether introduced voluntarily or mandatorily, RPs have the potential to become pivotal in achieving Europe's energy efficiency and decarbonization goals, fostering a future where renovations are strategic, impactful, and inclusive.

Round table 2 - Enhanced energy performance certificate

Figure 5. Participants in round table, from left to right: Vincenzo Corrado, Boris Sučić , Licinio Alfaro and Francesca Pagliaro

Moderation:

Vincenzo Corrado - Politecnico di Torino | Italy

Speakers:

Licinio Alfaro - Head of Department of Sustainable Construction at ITeC, Spain

Francesca Pagliaro - Researcher at ENEA, Italy

Boris Sučić - Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

The discussion opened with Vincenzo Corrado summarizing the six essential components of an enhanced EPC developed in the TIMEPAC project. These components emphasise data quality, holistic parameters, advanced technologies, renovation roadmaps, continuous updates, and user flexibility.

After this introduction, the following issues were proposed for the panellists to discuss:

- How can we ensure the quality of EPCs?
- What added value would incorporating real-time or historical operational data, along with static data, bring to EPCs?
- Would it be beneficial to integrate EPCs with additional certification frameworks, such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)?
- How could energy auditing, the Smart Readiness Indicator, and energy performance certification processes be integrated?
- What is the potential for creating national databases on the energy performance of buildings, and how could these be made interoperable with the EU Building Stock Observatory?
- How can EPCs be effectively utilised as a driving force for significant energy efficiency improvements in existing buildings?

The subsequent discussion with the panellists and audience addressed the following issues:

Data quality and data interoperability

- We need to have reliable data to ensure that EPCs are actionable for citizens and policymakers. The complex certification process in Italy, for example, involving multiple stakeholders and data transfer between regional and national databases, can lead to inconsistencies.
- To enhance data quality, it is crucial providing mandatory training for energy assessors and implementing local controls to verify the accuracy of EPCs before issuance.
- Interoperability emerged as a critical theme, focusing on the connection of various databases and standardised data collection across regions. Current discrepancies complicate the harmonization process at the national and at European level, as effective strategies depend on consistent information across Member States.

Holistic approach to energy performance

- A main challenge is to broaden the scope of current EPCs integrating performance indicators beyond energy efficiency to include indoor environmental quality, sustainability, affordability, and climate resilience.
- There is also a need for EPCs to reflect operational data and consider factors like climate change impacts and building safety, moving beyond their traditional energy-focused nature.
- The importance of including climate resilience data in EPCs was underscored, especially in light of recent climate-related disasters. Such information is increasingly relevant to prospective buyers and can enhance the value of EPCs.

User-centric communication

- EPCs need to be understandable and relevant to building owners and tenants. Facilitating accessibility and understanding EPC information for the general public is a concern. Many individuals do not understand energy performance metrics but can relate to financial implications, such as energy costs. Incorporating financial projections and climate resilience information into EPCs will make them more actionable for homeowners
- Therefore, there is a need to provide EPC data in user-friendly language and formats, making it easier for non-experts to comprehend. It is important to translate technical jargon into understandable language for homeowners and policymakers

Leveraging technology for enhanced EPCs

- Although operational data can enable more dynamic and accurate EPCs, there are difficulties to get it due to privacy concerns and GDPR compliance.
- The integration of smart meter data and the creation of a comprehensive digital model that incorporates various data types, such as climate impact and water usage, can provide a fuller understanding of building performance.
- Concerns were raised about the feasibility of creating a single, comprehensive data model that encompasses all aspects of a building's performance. A more practical approach was proposed, advocating for multiple, interconnected models, each tailored to specific needs such as energy analysis, acoustic assessment, or lifecycle analysis.

Implementation challenges

- There is a strong need to combine EPC initiatives with existing energy efficiency directives and regulatory frameworks. Proposals were made to integrate various audits, such as Smart Readiness Indicator audits, to streamline processes and reduce costs for end-users.
- Participants agreed on the need to transition from planning to actionable measures while being open to adjustments, underscoring the necessity for adaptable approaches that consider local contexts and constraints.
- The discussion also touched on differing realities, such as challenges faced in the Ivory Coast, underscoring the necessity for adaptable approaches that consider local contexts and constraints.

In sum, the roundtable discussion emphasised the urgent need for reforms in the EPC framework to make it more robust, user-friendly, and capable of driving substantial improvements in building energy performance. Participants recognised the importance of collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and industry professionals to build a system that supports informed decision-making and promotes a sustainable built environment. The discussion demonstrated a strong commitment to advancing the effectiveness of EPCs through a combination of technological innovation, cross-sector collaboration, and user-focused design.

Round table 3 - Improving building assessment through data integration

Figure 6. Participants in round table, from left to right: Álvaro Sicilia, Rolando Biere, Gloria Calleja and Thomas Bednar

Moderation:

Álvaro Sicilia - La Salle-URL

Speakers:

Thomas Bednar - Professor, Head of Department at TU Wien, Austria

Rolando Biere - Polytechnic University of Catalonia, Spain

Gloria Calleja - CEMOSA, Spain

The round table opened with Álvaro Sicilia introducing key topics addressed in TIMEPAC: the readiness of EPC databases for the EPBD recast, the accuracy of stored data, and the potential of BIM to improve EPC data quality. These themes set the stage for a focused discussion on enhancing data reliability and leveraging technology for better building performance assessments. The questions posed to panellists were the following:

- How can BIM improve Energy Performance Certification (EPC), Renovation Passports (RP), and Digital Building Logbooks (DBL)?
- What are the primary barriers to adopting BIM for improving EPC, RP, and DBL, and how can these barriers be overcome?
- What are the main challenges in data integration among BIM, EPC, RP, and DBL?
- What is the long-term potential of integrated building data in supporting sustainable and energy-efficient building practices?

The following issues were discussed in the subsequent conversation between the panellists and the audience:

Preparedness of EPC Databases

- We need to identify gaps in current EPC databases while exploring innovative methods like BIM for enhancing compliance with evolving EPBD requirement
- Many databases lacked integration with renovation passport data, though improvements were anticipated.

BIM and EPC integration

- BIM has potential to enhance EPCs, renovation passports, and building logbooks by improving data accuracy and providing dynamic information.
- However, there are these challenges:
 - Compatibility issues between BIM models for construction and energy certification.
 - Geographical factors like climate affecting BIM's effectiveness.
 - High costs and complexity for residential buildings.
 - Lack of skilled users and outdated data exchange methods.

Industry feedback and adoption barriers

- The industry struggles with:
 - Legacy data methods creating interoperability challenges.
 - Limited integration of BIM for older or heritage buildings.
 - Disconnection between software systems for construction and energy performance.
- BIM holds value for lifecycle tracking and maintenance but faces obstacles:
 - Data integration issues across platforms (BIM, EPCs, digital logbooks).
 - End-user training and technical gaps.

Standardization and complexity of building data

- Building data is highly fragmented and lacks standardization.
- Dynamic factors (e.g., heat, moisture, sensor data) and diverse professional practices add complexity.
- Current standards like IFC are insufficient, prompting calls for updates or alternative methods.

Open source and collaboration needs

- Universities can drive open-source innovations, but industry inertia and limited collaboration hinder progress.
- Emerging standards and technologies, such as linked data and semantic web, could improve interoperability.

Broader benefits and strategic Integration

- Data integration optimises building assessments and aligns with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).
- Involving all stakeholders—governments, developers, and families—is essential for adoption.

Circular economy and digital twins

- Integrated data aids in assessing component performance for reuse and system efficiency via digital twins.

Audience questions and key reflections

The audience raised concerns about:

- Sustainability of vast data storage.
 - Digital tools like digital twins should be environmentally sustainable, avoiding unnecessary carbon emissions if not essential in the long term.
 - Existing data, such as that from smart meters, offers valuable insights and can be leveraged alongside newer systems like digital building logbooks
- Balancing privacy with data accessibility.
 - The utility of BIM depends on the context and the permissions granted by building owners.
 - Real estate professionals may benefit from BIM access, but privacy, legal, and role-specific requirements must guide the scope of shared data
- Simplifying BIM for specific use cases.
 - Difficulty of balancing complexity with usability.
 - Simplified models, tailored to users' needs, are more effective but require ongoing feedback and collaboration.
- Tokenization and data management
 - Clear guidelines are needed for who can generate, manage, and use data to ensure structured and secure global data management.

In conclusion, while the preparedness of EPC databases and the integration of BIM into energy performance systems hold great potential for enhancing building management and sustainability, significant challenges remain. These include issues of data interoperability, compatibility between BIM and EPC systems, and the complexity of building data. The lack of integration with renovation passport data, coupled with outdated data exchange methods and the high costs associated with BIM implementation, continue to hinder widespread adoption. However, the industry's increasing recognition of these challenges, coupled with emerging technologies like open-source innovations and digital twins, presents opportunities for future advancements. For successful adoption, collaboration between governments, developers, universities, and stakeholders is crucial, along with the standardization of data practices and careful attention to privacy concerns. Ultimately, the strategic integration of these tools can significantly contribute to more efficient, sustainable, and circular building practices in line with regulatory frameworks such as the EPBD.

5 Papers

These papers, presented in-person at the conference, were selected through an open call and evaluated by members of the scientific committee.

Local Levelised Cost of Energy: Enhancing the SRI and EPC with financial indicators

Rolf Bastiaanssen

Bax & Company, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract. European policy on energy efficiency in buildings has led to the development of two certification schemes: the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) and the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI). The EPC provides an energy performance rating and is intended to offer recommendations for cost-effective improvements, while the SRI rates the smart readiness of buildings across nine technical domains and seven desired impacts. However, neither certification currently includes a measure of cost-effectiveness. This study proposes using Local Levelised Cost of Energy (LLCOE) as an indicator of energy system cost-effectiveness, with a focus on consumer-centric, integrated, and context-specific criteria. LLCOE represents the unit cost of energy (e.g., €/kWh) for a defined local energy system setup, covering capital investment in generation, storage, and distribution, as well as operating costs, financing, taxes, and remaining grid energy purchases, over a standard economic lifetime. To demonstrate this approach, LLCOE was calculated for a multi-family building in the Netherlands under two scenarios: one relying on grid energy purchases (LLCOE €0.189/kWh), and one with a system integrating PV, storage, and flexibility services (LLCOE €0.127/kWh). This initial analysis illustrates the potential of LLCOE as a practical, recognizable metric for long-term end-user costs. Future calculations will need to draw from existing data and methods to minimise certification burdens and may require interdisciplinary collaboration. The insights gained could guide the development of strategies to enhance self-consumption and energy efficiency in buildings and urban areas.

Keywords: Energy Performance Certificate, Smart Readiness Indicators, Local Energy Systems, Levelised Cost Of Energy, Local Levelised Cost of Energy

1. Introduction

Europe's building stock is generally old and energy-inefficient, accounting for 40% of total energy consumption and 36% of energy-related CO₂ emissions. The European Green Deal outlines energy efficiency goals and strategies to reduce CO₂ emissions, environmental impacts, and promote sustainability, circular economy, and resilience. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), established in 2018 and revised in 2024, serves as the primary regulatory framework aimed at achieving a fully decarbonised building stock by 2050.

European policy on energy efficiency in buildings has led to the development of two certifications that provide information on the performance of buildings for both policy-makers and consumers aiming to buy or rent a building. The Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) includes an energy performance rating and is widely used. The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) is more recent and measures the smart readiness of buildings; their ability to sense, interpret, communicate and actively respond in an efficient manner to changing conditions in relation to the operation of technical building systems, the external environment (including energy grids) and the demands of building occupants.

1.1 Problem statement

Sesana (2018) claims that building owners often avoid energy-saving investments due to the lack of reliable information and/or uncertainties regarding potential financial and environmental benefits.

The European Commission's revised EPBD (EUR-Lex, 2024) places greater emphasis on prioritizing renovations for buildings where improvements are most cost-effective and yield the highest energy savings. However, economic viability is only briefly addressed, limited to achieving zero-emission buildings and enhancing indoor environments. For operational cost-efficiency, the revised EPBD

highlights building automation and control systems (BACS) as tools to support both energy efficiency and economical building operation. Currently, neither the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) nor the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) includes a direct measure of cost-effectiveness for building systems, although the EPC does provide recommendations to enhance system cost-effectiveness.

In this study we propose to enrich the EPC and SRI frameworks with at least one economic indicator on cost-effectiveness; signposting the cost of energy associated with ratings of a building. This would create a pathway for building owners to invest in renovations and equip policymakers with a tool to design effective measures that promote smart readiness and the deep renovation of the EU building stock. Resulting insights could be presented to create viable, innovative strategies to boost self-consumption and energy efficiency in buildings and urban areas.

The paper is structured as follows: a literature review on the EPC and SRI indicators, along with relevant economic indicators, followed by a critical analysis that identifies gaps in the existing frameworks, specifically the absence of economic indicators, and evaluates the suitability of commonly used metrics like the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE). We then propose the LLCOE as a viable economic indicator for the two frameworks. The conclusions section discusses the significance of these findings, limitations of the study, and potential directions for future research.

2. Related work and analysis

Energy Performance Certificate

The EPC primarily focuses on a building's energy demand for heating and cooling, as determined by its structural characteristics, and tends to overlook energy generation capacities. Widely researched and in use across the European Union since the first EPBD was enacted in 2002, EPCs are currently among the key sources of information on the energy performance of the EU's building stock (Klitou, 2024). While the certificate's effectiveness is generally recognised, several researchers have identified its limitations and areas for improvement (Sesana, 2024).

The European Commission is currently considering a revision of the EPC through the Next Generation EPC-Cluster—a group of 10 research projects focused on EPC development (European Commission, 2022). Key objectives include improving tool accuracy, enhancing user interfaces, and increasing interoperability metrics. These advancements aim to make EPCs more reliable, user-friendly, and compatible with other systems (Klitou, 2024).

Smart Readiness Indicator

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) is an assessment scheme introduced by the European Commission in the 2018 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive to measure the “intelligence² of buildings (European Commission, 2024). The SRI evaluates services across seven impact categories, assessing their capacity to adapt to occupant needs, support maintenance and efficient operations, and respond dynamically to the energy grid.

The SRI includes nine asset-based domains—such as heating, cooling, hot water, lighting, EV charging, and monitoring and control—each with 2-5 levels of functionality. These domains are designed to support three primary objectives: optimizing energy efficiency and overall in-use performance, adapting to occupant needs, and responding to grid signals to enable energy flexibility.

As a novel policy instrument, the SRI has not yet been widely researched or published through peer review methods (Chatzikonstantinidis, 2022). Reports indicate that an accurate assessment of the SRI can identify buildings that contribute to energy generation and utility management, including generation and distribution (Plienaitis, 2023).

Current proposals for the SRI mainly focus on qualitative assessments of the smartness of buildings, often neglecting the wider context of districts, even as decisions about energy infrastructure, such as heat networks, are made on a larger scale (Märzinger, 2020). Tzani (2023) notes that while the existing format of the SRI is generally adequate, the solutions required to reach the maximum SRI are not really economically viable

Jenkins (2022) advocated for the use of economic indicators, such as a simple EPC kWh/y metric, but warns that end-users, including policy makers, may struggle to understand the context, calculations, and limitations associated with this value. Additionally, Papadopoulos (2024) suggests enhancing smart readiness indicators through simplified financial metrics, specifically employing whole life cycle costing.

Economic indicators

Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is an economic metric widely used by scientists, policymakers, and investors to optimise energy systems and energy efficiency (Jamil et al., 2022; Joskow, 2011; Matsuo, 2020). Szymanski (2020) describes LCOE as the average cost of generating a unit of electricity over the lifetime of a generation asset, encompassing both fixed and variable, while also highlighting inconsistencies in its economic definition.

Originally, LCOE served as a normalised cost for the generation of assets, providing a basis for setting prices in Power Purchase Agreement, which are essential for recovering investments in energy generation facilities. (Loth et al., 2022). Over time, its application has evolved to facilitate comparisons among different power generating technologies, allowing stakeholders to rank their options effectively.

Many authors have indicated the shortcomings of LCOE as a metric, particularly in the context of renewable energy sources and decentralised market models (Jamil et al., 2022; Joskow, 2011; Ueckerdt et al., 2013). Alternatives have been proposed to replace or augment LCOE for renewable system design, including LCOEx, or LCOEn (de Simón-Martín 2022), ISLA (Vargas-Salgado, 2022), and VALOCE (Abujarad, 2020).

In Bastiaanssen (2019), a new indicator known as the Local Levelised Cost of Energy (LLCOE) was proposed. This straightforward metric is expressed in €/kWh and pertains specifically to a Local Energy System (LES). LLCOE encompasses the capital investment, operating costs—including financing, taxes, and levies—over a standardised technical lifetime, as well as remaining energy purchases from the grid. Consequently, it quantifies the end-user cost per kWh for that LES. The LLCOE concept diverges from existing methods in several significant ways: 1) It emphasises consumer costs rather than asset costs, 2) It considers integrated system operating costs instead of focusing solely on individual assets, and 3) It adopts a tailored scope for the system rather than relying on a generic asset class indicator.

3. Case study

To evaluate the suitability of the Local Levelised Cost of Energy (LLCOE) for enhancing the certificates, this metric has been applied to a multi-family apartment building in Amersfoort, Netherlands. Two scenarios are compared: Scenario 1 involves purchasing electricity directly from the grid, and Scenario 2 includes the installation of a 100 kWp rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system and an 160kWh / 80 kW battery system, with a portion of the battery capacity utilised for imbalance trading.

Scale level	Multi-family residential	Consumption	167.926 kWh/y
Location	Amersfoort, the Netherlands	Electricity price	0,1494 €/kWh

Scenario 1: grid-provided energy			
	Per year	Per 15 year	
Grid Connection (kVa)	110 €	6.633 €	99.489 €
Consumption (kWh)	167.926 €	25.088 €	376.322 €
15-year Total cost	2.518.890 kWh	€ 475.811	
LLCOE (kWh)		€ 0,189	

Scenario 2: PV + Storage + imbalance trading + grid consumption			
	Per year	Per 15 year	
Grid Connection (kVa)	110 €	6.633 €	99.489 €
PV system	100kWP	€ 66.000	
BESS system	80kW / 160kWh	€ 100.000	
Maintenance, insurance	€ 1.500	€ 22.500	
Production PV (kWh/y)	85.000		
Net demand grid (kWh/y)	82.926	€ 12.389	€ 185.837
Imbalance trade revenue		-€ 17.563	-€ 263.445
Imbalance trade cost		€ 7.346	€ 110.190
25-year Total cost	2.518.890 kWh	€ 320.571	
LLCOE (kWh)		€ 0,127	

Figure 1. Comparing LLCOE for two alternative system set-ups in the case study location

The resulting LLCOE for Scenario 1 is €0,189/kWh, the LLCOE for Scenario 2 is €0,127/kWh (Figure 1). In this analysis, the energy demand and prices are derived from real data. The costs associated with the photovoltaic (PV) system, battery energy storage system (BESS), and maintenance are based on quotes from installation companies, normalised for a 15-year period to account for the longer lifetime of PV systems. Additionally, revenues and costs related to flexibility services are estimated based on information from specialised service providers.

3.1 Positioning and reflections

The purpose of European policy is to promote the greening of its building stock. There is a general consensus that the EPC and SRI contribute positively to informing consumers about the energy performance and smart readiness of buildings. However, it has been suggested that this information is utilised more effectively by local policymakers than by consumers. In both instances, the effectiveness of these certificates and indicators in signposting the cost-effectiveness of existing systems or potential improvements is considered unclear or low, which inevitably discourages action from both stakeholder groups.

The LLCOE was originally conceived to assess, compare, and analyse investment options within complex, "smart" multi-building energy systems, where specific investments in assets lead to a price per energy unit (e.g., €/kWh over the asset's lifetime). This approach shifts the focus from the performance of individual assets to the overall system performance, thus providing an end-user perspective, which aligns with suggestions to enhance building certificates.

The LLCOE concept demonstrates significant versatility, making it applicable to various scales, from large districts and cities to individual buildings. This versatility allows it to effectively inform decision-making across multiple levels of the energy system. Therefore, this indicator appears to have the potential to address the gaps identified in research by providing end-users with actionable insights. At the same time, LLCOE does not strictly align with the scope of EPCs or SRIs as it adopts a comprehensive end-user perspective on total energy consumption, rather than focusing solely on building services.

Links with EPC and SRI

EPCs indicate energy efficiency in terms of a balance between demand, savings and generation capacities. A higher score reflects greater energy efficiency corresponding to lower net energy demand. The recommendations provided by EPCs offer qualitative insights into the operating cost of a building based on average comfort levels, whereas LLCOE quantifies these aspects. While it does not estimate how to reduce energy demand, it does provide an indication of the unit cost of energy based on a given system design and estimated total demand. Additionally, LLCOE can be framed in terms of payback, similar to the recommendations for improvements found in EPCs.

From an economic perspective, LLCOE encompasses all domains listed in SRI and shares a highly similar scope. It covers financials related to two of the three SRI functionalities: overall in-use performance and adaptation to grid signals (excluding adaptability to occupants' needs). LLCOE achieves this by incorporating the financials of all assets, management services, and other costs, as well as the net demand from the grid and grid services.

Reflections on practice calculating LLCOE

Literature suggests that any additional indicator should be based on existing data collection methods or require no additional efforts or skills from certifiers. Since LLCOE has not yet been validated in practice, its alignment with these requirements cannot currently be assessed.

Several operational aspects need further assessment to verify the fit for purpose of the LLCOE approach. Preliminary exploration indicates that its effectiveness relies on a variety of data, including energy consumption and generation, as well as a detailed understanding of energy markets, such as energy prices and emerging flexibility markets.

From a methodological standpoint, uncertainties arise concerning the long-term development of costs and prices, particularly regarding volatile energy prices and flexibility markets. Additional uncertainties include the differences between estimated and actual investment and operating costs, as well as factors related to changes in the building or local energy system's scope. For example, the introduction of new users or an increase in demand or generation capacity over time may alter the system balance, thereby affecting the cost of energy for that system.

These considerations may limit the viability of LLCOE as an easily calculable metric for inclusion in certification of the certification of buildings. However, it may be possible to provide alternative type of results, such as indications of expected building energy costs in relation to benchmarked similar systems for which LLCOE has already been calculated. This would still provide a pathway for owners to invest in renovations and could provide policymakers with a valuable tool to design realistic instruments to support smart readiness and deep renovation of the EU building stock.

4. Conclusions

Europe needs to accelerate action in addressing climate change and improving energy efficiency in buildings, which requires significant investment. While main regulatory frameworks and related certifications highlight the importance of cost-efficiency, they do not provide guidance or a formal assessment of current system performance or potential improvements. This represents a weakness in the implementation strategy.

Using emerging indicators from the field of local energy systems, such as LLCOE, presents a promising opportunity to enhance metrics for the built environment. These indicators could enrich the EPC and SRI by providing stakeholders with meaningful, actionable information through simple or simplified indicators. They could thus provide policymakers and investors with viable, innovative strategies to boost self-consumption and improve energy efficiency in buildings and urban areas.

It remains unclear to what extent the use of LLCOE or similar indicators can be integrated in EPC or SRI, and whether this integration would require additional data collection or assessment by certifiers. Multi-disciplinary collaboration is essential for further analyse of this topic and for validating the concept through theoretical or applied research.

Further research is necessary to explore the extent to which LLCOE or similar indicators could be derived from existing data collection methods and the current skills of certifiers. Additionally, further refinement of LLCOE as an indicator is recommended. Finally, conducting design studies or pilot studies to assess LLCOE would provide valuable information that could potentially validate these methods.

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Towards seamless data integration through an open data model

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Abstract. Various agents are involved in the different stages of the lifecycle of a building, from its planning to its operation, and they use different tools to carry out their tasks. With the help of Building Information Modelling (BIM), the working method for the networked planning, construction, and management of buildings and other structures can be facilitated through the use of software applications to digitally model, combine, record, and exchange relevant building data. In practice, this exchange usually only works well with a pre-established combination of tools as the digital information flow can be hindered if agents use external applications such as simulation tools. Typically, only documents are exchanged, or limited effort is made to move forward using digital exports. These can be, for example, based on the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standard. Although IFC is an international standard, it can be customised and agents can then create “dialects” that various tools may interpret differently. As a result, any form of data integration must be manually checked and often has to be corrected and supplemented, which can lead to possible errors and redundancies. This is a time-consuming process. Ultimately, these tasks are carried out at the expense of critical design work, such as variant investigations and discussions to find the best possible solution.

To tackle this challenge, we use the advantages of software development in Model-Driven Engineering (MDE). We provide an open metamodel where stakeholders can create their data structures as required based on generic parts, which are automatically compatible with the data structures of other experts that conform to the same metamodel. These data structures are machine-readable and can be used to integrate different tools. In addition, it is also possible to map standards in the same format so that validations and reference implementations are available in a machine-readable exchange form. In this work, we demonstrate the applicability of our approach in multiple use cases. The application areas encompass various simulations, geometry, and automation, while the project scale ranges from detailed single buildings to entire city districts.

Keywords: Interoperable, Metamodel, Integration, BIM, MDE

1. Introduction

The Building Information Modelling (BIM) concept involves consistently utilizing digital building models throughout the entire lifecycle of a building—from its planning and realization to the operational and demolition phases. The foundation for virtual building models was laid in the 1970s when Eastman published a concept on the construction and use of such models (Eastman, 1975). Van Needervan and Tolman (1992) later coined the term BIM. A significant advantage of such digital models is their ability to facilitate lossless information exchange which is indispensable for effective interoperability (dos Santos et al., 2017). The level of interoperability in BIM models varies depending on the type of BIM being used. “Little BIM” refers to using specific BIM software by an individual planner, where BIM is applied without external communication (Jernigan, 2008). On the other hand, “Big BIM” refers to the consistent, model-based communication among all stakeholders throughout all the phases of a building’s lifecycle. Furthermore, BIM can be classified as either “closed” or “open”, based on whether vendor-neutral data exchange formats are utilised (Borrmann et al., 2015).

To establish a model-based communication and support the information exchange over digital models, the tools developed in Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) might offer a helpful solution. In MDE, formal machine-readable models are the central artifacts for the engineering process Brambilla et al., 2017). Such readable and processable representations allow for different viewpoints on systems. To be able

to represent the observed reality in formal models, dedicated modelling languages (e.g., UML¹) for defining both the grammar and the context are used.

An established and widely adopted standard for BIM is the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) definition (buildingSMART, 2024). IFC models encompass both geometric data and metadata on building objects, facilitating interoperability among various tools. However, there are some challenges related to model-based interoperability when exchanging building data models, especially via IFC (Steel et al., 2012). One crucial challenge is the inconsistency of modelling styles, where the modelling language should describe all possibilities thoroughly and unambiguously to avoid unexpected alternatives. In addition, several approaches for open and closed BIM solutions have been proposed to address the complexity of synchronizing different types of information within complex systems (Pólit-Casillas & Howe, 2013; Volk et al., 2014).

One of the central features of BIM is the coupling of geometry and alphanumeric data. However, there are a multitude of approaches to that task. On the one hand, in the IFC, the coupling is very loose and is realised via the concept of *geometric representation of the subtypes of IfcProduct and data assignment to the subtypes of IfcObjectDefinition* (buildingSMART, 2024). On the other hand, the coupling can be very tight, allowing for arbitrarily complex data to be attached to any geometric primitive (e.g., vertex) (Steiner et al., 2024). The advantage of the first approach is that the data can be effectively encapsulated and easily managed. The second approach allows for more complex interdependencies between data and geometry but also may be more difficult to manage in the absence of robust organizational and compliance-checking infrastructure. However, the normative base of any technical discipline can be utilised in the development of such infrastructure.

When we speak of *data*, it is useful to differentiate between the *semantic-free* data stream from a sensor (here, the meaning of the symbol sequence is only implicit) and the specialised model with explicit *semantics* defined for a particular task, e.g., simulation. The second kind of data can act as the basis for efficient integration due to the fine-grained control that the explicit semantics can provide. In fact, there has been extensive research on the methods for *semantic enrichment* of BIM models (Sacks et al., 2017). However, even semantically rich data, when in large quantities and in a context lacking sufficient standardization, can become difficult to manage (Borghoff et al., 2022; Zhao & Taib, 2022).

To meet this challenge, we developed a data integration methodology that regards the production and maintenance of technical guidelines at the same level as the design of BIM models. However, unlike an ordinary BIM model, the technical guidelines, written in or translated to a *formal language*, act as the *source* of the semantic backbone of data integration in BIM models. This removes the danger of conflicting or redundant user-defined semantics and improves the chances of preserving model continuity across multiple project phases (Miettinen & Paavola, 2014), one of the major tenets of BIM. The method we apply allows us to model complex, and even partially overlapping, domain-specific semantics *without* introducing any additional ones, as we strictly separate semantics and syntax.

The remainder of this paper is as follows: In Section 2, we describe the approach of our open data model Simultan in a conceptualised way. Section 3 shows different application use cases from geometry over automation and simulation. Finally, Section 4 concludes our paper and gives a short outlook.

¹ Unified Modeling Language, <https://www.uml.org/>

2. Open data model towards seamless data integration

In this section, we present our methodology of an open data model towards managing seamless data integration based on MDE methods.

Figure 1. Levels of interoperability according to ISO 11354-1: the federated and integrated approaches

Seamless data integration has already been subject to standardization efforts, among others, in ISO 11354-1. This standard distinguishes between the federated model, where data exchange between models cannot rely on semantic commonalities (see the left-hand side of Figure 1), and the integrated model, where there are some partial commonalities (see the right-hand side of Figure 1). In the federated model, communication between digital models is restricted to the *communication layer*, which in itself holds no knowledge but is capable of transferring information, e.g., in the form of an IFC file. In the integrated model, part of the communication already takes place within the *semantic layer*. This layer holds domain knowledge, for example, based on agreed-upon technical guidelines enabling it to transfer information while also validating it for conformance with requirements, consistency, plausibility, and computability, among other criteria. Beside these two models, there is also the unified model, which allows communication only within the semantic layer, but in the context of the construction industry, it is, at the moment, somewhat aspirational. The semantic commonalities that enhance the integrated model over the federated one are built upon a shared *metamodel*. Therefore, our methodology is grounded in this kind of common open *metamodel*.

In digitalization, we frequently refer to digital *models*, meaning digital representations of real-world objects (such as an existing building) or concepts (such as a building in the planning phase). The relationship between a metamodel and its *conforming* models is comparable to the relationship between LEGO® bricks (The LEGO Group, 2024) and any LEGO® models that can be assembled with them. In Figure 2, we illustrate the conceptual difference between models that conform to a common metamodel (Model A1 to Model A3) and those that do not (Model B). At the top of the figure, *Metamodel A* defines basic building blocks and specifies how they interact to accomplish various tasks. At the bottom right, there are three different models –Model A1, Model A2, and Model A3–, all of which *conform* to *Metamodel A*, meaning

Figure 2. The relationship between a metamodel and the models conforming to it

they are constructed exclusively from its defined building blocks. Although each model appears distinct, using the same building blocks allows them to “communicate” with one another—facilitating data exchange and even enabling integration into larger, more complex models.

Model B is the most commonly used practice (Borghoff et al., 2022), and represents a proprietary, closed, even “black box” model. If the building blocks of this model are completely hidden, we cannot exchange any meaningful data with it, unless it offers a file import interface. Even when the model’s building blocks are visible, if they do not come from *Metamodel A*, it is impossible to perform data integration between Model B and, for example, Model A2 without designing a dedicated translation service. However, if Model B incorporates a building block from *Metamodel A*, as in the *Hybrid Model* in Figure 2, then data integration becomes possible within the scope defined in this one building block, e.g., a CO_2 footprint calculation.

We created a metamodel consisting of around 50 different basic types that can be dynamically combined into increasingly complex models (Paskaleva et al., 2018; 2019a, 2019b). Thus, domain experts can create custom data structures for any specific task, which are automatically compatible with the data structures of other stakeholders (Paskaleva et al., 2022).

However, if all the digital models in our work environment *must* conform to *Metamodel A*, can it truly capture all the semantics across the diverse domains of the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry, the Facility Management (FM), and building and infrastructure operations? The answer is no. We already have a large normative base that contains all relevant semantics, that is to say, all term definitions, workflows, calculations, and reference examples. In our methodology, we translate guidelines that, up to now, are available only as a downloadable PDF file into a *formalised machine-readable representation* (Paskaleva et al., 2024). Just as a LEGO® model requires not only LEGO® bricks but also instructions for building, these formal guideline representations act as the instructions for the assembly of models out of the building blocks in *Metamodel A*. For example, Model A1 could be built according to ISO 6946 for the simplified calculation of thermal transmittance and Model A2 could be built according to ISO 10211 for the detailed calculation of thermal bridges. However, since both guidelines rely on the same *taxonomy* (semantics) and both models contain the same building blocks of *Metamodel A* (syntax), they can perform seamless data integration, both semantically and syntactically. Of course, the exchange with other digital models, which do not conform to *Metamodel A*, is always possible on the *communication layer* via import and export in various file formats. It is just a question of translating, for example, from *Metamodel A* to IFC, XML², JSON³ or other standards.

² eXtensible Markup Language

³ JavaScript Object Notation

2.1 Towards integration of standards

According to the established data integration landscape illustrated in Figure 3, users employ specialised software that, in some cases, communicates through a shared collaborative platform, which provides data storage and predefined workflows. One example of such a workflow is the ability for one user to flag issues in another model and receive notifications about potential resolutions. However, ensuring that each digital model complies with all relevant technical guidelines is still manual, time-consuming, and error-prone.

We propose an alternative solution that treats the development of technical guidelines as just another task within the AEC industries. Figure 4 illustrates the role of standardization as a provider of reference digital models and implementations that can be integrated into project-specific custom digital models, ensuring automatic compliance with each respective guideline.

Figure 3. The current landscape of data integration and collaboration

Figure 4. The data integration landscape and collaboration proposed in our methodology

Currently, message- or file-based communication is the standard method (see Figure 3). However, our methodology is transitioning toward *model-based* communication (see the additional communication channels in Figure 4). This shift enables not only data exchange but also guarantees compliance with technical guidelines. Such a transition is key to facilitate the data integration

strategy introduced in this section, where guideline compliance checks are conducted in the *semantic layer*, while less critical tasks are managed in the semantic-free *communication layer*.

The next step involves developing *digital technical guidelines* that serve as direct instructions for the automated construction of *digital models*. Validation examples created alongside such guidelines can be collectively utilised as a verification method, ensuring that a model claiming compliance with a guideline genuinely meets all its requirements.

3. Application use cases

The methodology we described at the conceptual level in Section 2 can be applied in multiple domains of the AEC and FM industries. This universal applicability makes it an excellent means of communication between domains that often have very different viewpoints due to the different focus of each domain.

Geometry

Our methodology can be applied to the geometry of the digital model. Since different domain experts require different geometric representations of the same structure, which are, at the same time, interdependent (such as architectural and structural engineering geometry), we can apply the same mechanism depicted in Figure 2. In essence, we use the same geometric primitives, *vertices*, *edges*, *faces*, and *volumes*, to construct complex geometric models that meet specific *formalised requirements*. In Steiner et al. (2024) we presented an example of the procedural generation of the material layers and structural elements of a building out of simple reference geometry and formal parameterised descriptions of wall, edge, and corner details in Grasshopper and Rhinoceros®. Relationships (such as *contained in* or *aligned with*) between the geometric primitives at the metamodel level ensure the consistency among the geometric representations across different domains. This consistency guarantees that digital geometry models conform to the same geometry metamodel. As a result, for instance, if a wall is moved in the architectural model, this change is communicated to the structural model, prompting the user with an alert or suggesting adjustments to the corresponding structural members.

This methodology can be scaled up to represent entire city districts or large infrastructures, such as airports (Forster et al., 2018). By using the same metamodel elements to construct digital geometry models at various levels of granularity (comparable to BIM levels of geometry), we ensure seamless communication and appropriate responses to updates. For instance, if a building's LOG400 (highly detailed) geometry is modified in one model, its corresponding representation in LOG100 (depicting only the building envelope) within a city district model will also update automatically, without requiring user intervention.

Integration of Calculation Tools

Another application field is the integration of already existing calculation or simulation tools, for example, tables, formulas and macros in Excel®. Many legacy tools are developed in parallel with various technical guidelines containing reference implementations (David et al., 2017). Our methodology enables the integration of such tools by providing metamodel elements for the representation of spreadsheets and the implicit semantics contained in the distribution and content of various cell ranges, user interface elements, or VBA⁴ code (Paskaleva et al., 2021). This is made possible by providing metamodel-level relationships, which allow for the formulation of rules for mapping various existing model elements onto specific cells in the spreadsheet, both as input and output. In this way, legacy tools can become part of newly developed digital models, thereby preserving existing knowledge and applying it to new projects.

⁴ Visual Basic for Applications

Another application is formulating the requirements on digital models in a familiar environment, such as Excel®. This allows the domain experts to design their own data models without the involvement of software engineers (Paskaleva et al., 2023). The metamodel behind this application enables the automated transfer of information from the spreadsheet into a UML class diagram, which can be automatically translated into code and tested. This removes a massive communication barrier between disciplines and prevents time losses in designing new digital models and tools for traditional development cycles.

Building Automation

In building automation, we have used our method to promote platform-independent representation of control logic. This makes it possible to describe logical control functions in both textual and machine-readable formats from the early stages of the design phase (Knorr et al., 2024). In the next step, these descriptions are automatically translated for simulations and later for execution. The digital information can be kept in the data metamodel (Sint et al., 2024). The implementation was evaluated by using an example of a ventilation system.

Simulation

Simulations represent another crucial application area for digital models. In building HVAC⁵ and neighbourhood simulations, many different tools must process information from these digital models. Automated exchange offers significant advantages, as it eliminates the need for multiple entries of existing information and allows changes to be made in a single location. Consequently, the simulation can be re-run efficiently. We have demonstrated that an automated connection to IDA-ICE for building physics simulations and to RFEM for structural analysis is feasible (Steiner et al., 2023). In our data model structure, all relevant information (such as parameters and geometry) for a hygrothermal building simulation is stored. This means that only an automatic transformation to the structure of the IDA-ICE simulation tool is needed to execute the simulation. This automated transformation allows for the repeated simulation of different buildings and variants without requiring any changes through the interface. This process ensures a continuous digital flow, propagating all changes from the simulation tool to any other tools that require updates. Figure 5 shows the flow from the geometry and structural data to IDA-ICE, where the hygrothermal simulation is carried out. Following this, the results are transferred back into the data model (Steiner et al., 2023).

Another application demonstrates the automated creation of simulation models for digital twins, significantly reducing the modelling effort while ensuring the consistency and timeliness of the digital twin (Bühler & Bednar, 2024). The method seamlessly integrates different aspects of model creation, from the initial geometry generation to the final post-processing phase, by embedding the metamodel in Python - a widely used language in building simulation. The interface provides access to various Python libraries and APIs for applications. The application was evaluated using a detailed simulation of thermally activated component systems using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) (Bühler & Bednar, 2024).

⁵ Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning

Figure 5. Depiction of the connections and the direction of data exchange between the SIMULTAN data model and the simulation software IDA-ICE based on Steiner et al., 2023

Scalability

Regarding the scalability of our methodology, we successfully scaled the application from the building level to the district level in further implementations in cooperation with Vienna Airport and the municipality of Bruck an der Leitha. Digital models of over 200 buildings and networks, such as the electricity grid and cooling network, were created and analysed. Interactions and interdependencies between different areas can also be examined in this context. For example, the influence of electromobility and heat pumps on the electricity consumption of buildings and residential zones can be examined⁶.

4 . Conclusion and outlook

We have introduced an MDE-based approach to data integration in the context of BIM that relies on a common open metamodel, which enables seamless communication between all models or model parts conforming to it. This allows us to transform domain-specific technical guidelines or contractual requirements into explicit semantic support for communication, tool interoperability, and data integration. The use cases we present demonstrate our solution’s versatility and scalability. In essence, digital models can be designed to be guideline-compliant by default. Furthermore, various calculation and simulation tools from the AEC industry domains can communicate their requirements to any data model created according to our method and automatically meet those requirements. The result is BIM models that grow organically with the involvement of additional project stakeholders. Such models hold the amount of information needed to perform a particular task, no more and no less. This contributes to the streamlining of digital models, making them smaller and easier to manage and query since their elements reflect well-known semantics. In the end, this contributes to the digital sustainability in BIM.

In our future work, we intend to outline a roadmap for adapting existing technical guidelines into *formalised representations* and designing new guidelines as fully functional digital models. These

⁶ <https://nachhaltigwirtschaften.at/de/sdz/projekte/smart-q-plus-bruck-an-der-leitha.php>

models will have the capability to *declare* and *enforce* requirements on other project-specific digital models.

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Configurations and qualities of new office building in Barcelona to meet current and new regulatory requirements

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Abstract. Since 2010, the European Union (EU) has introduced regulatory frameworks aimed at improving energy efficiency, reducing primary energy consumption, and minimizing environmental impacts across all sectors. The 2019 update to Spain's Technical Building Code (CTE DB HE), which includes the Nearly Zero-Energy Building (nZEB) requirements, aligns with these EU goals. This study assesses the impact of these energy-saving regulations on new office buildings in Barcelona, with a focus on the current compliance scenarios and exploring potential future scenarios that exceed existing standards. The study employs a unified methodology to analyse 622,081 building configuration scenarios, evaluating them against the minimum energy performance standards and compliance indicators established by CTE DB HE 2019 and the EU's Recast Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). The results show that while nearly half of the scenarios comply with Zero Energy Building (ZEB) standards, more stringent energy limits would significantly improve compliance. The study identifies key parameters—such as lighting efficiency, thermal envelope quality, and renewable energy use—that can optimise compliance with both current and future regulations. The findings suggest that Barcelona's building sector has the potential to achieve more ambitious energy efficiency goals, even under current technical and economic constraints. Furthermore, the study provides a methodology for future applications in both new and existing buildings to meet climate neutrality targets and reduce carbon emissions in the built environment.

Keywords: Energy efficiency, nZEB, ZEB, Building regulations, EPC

1. Introduction

Since 2010, the EU has proposed new regulatory requirements as a new "paradigm" to achieve ambitious objectives in energy efficiency, primary energy consumption reduction, and environmental impact for all sectors of society. In December 2019, the updated CTE DB HE (Ministerio de Transportes, 2019)—Basic Document for Energy Saving of the Spanish Technical Building Code (CTE)(Gobierno de España, 2022) was published, which essentially applied the regulatory requirements from the European Union to the national context of Spain and defined the conditions of compliance for nearly zero-energy buildings (nZEB).

This study evaluates the impact of the 2010 CTE DB HE energy-saving regulations on the design of new office buildings in Barcelona. It aims to assess current minimum compliance scenarios and explore future scenarios with higher energy efficiency standards, potentially surpassing existing regulatory requirements.

Most of the regulatory requirements applicable in Barcelona are based on the prescriptive or performance values of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) established by Spanish Codes (Gobierno de España, 2021). Therefore, the EPC becomes a framework for standardizing behaviour to be verified by the local ordinances and regulations (Govern de Catalunya, 2006) as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Summary of current and future regulations and requirements in the building sector in Barcelona

To conduct this study, a unified approach was essential to define objectives, establish methodology, and devise strategies for future development. This integrated vision also helped manage the operational complexity of interconnected processes and domains. In Barcelona, where various regulatory codes can apply to buildings, this approach was particularly critical. The study framework was thus developed to address specific questions:

- What are the minimum configurations and qualities in new office buildings in Barcelona in relation to the requirements of CTE-HE 2019 (nZEB)?
- What are the configurations and qualities in new office buildings in Barcelona regarding the future evolution of the European directive (ZEB, EPBD Recast)? (European Parliament, 2021)
- What is the best-case scenario that can be achieved with optimal configurations, considering realistic technical and economic feasibility scenarios?

2. Methodology: Parameters and indicators

The study is built upon an analysis of different combinations of building configurations, through modifying specific parameters and evaluating their effect on a set of indicators. The methodology is summarised in the diagrams in Figure 2 (see further detail in Appendix A).

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the methodology

The parameters used to define the different configurations are as follows (Table 1):

- **Occupancy and Operational Conditions (OOC):** This parameter addresses how the building is used and its level of internal load. The operational conditions and usage profiles of the building correspond to those established in the *Recognised Document of Energy Certification of Buildings in Spanish codes* (Gobierno de España, 2020) which specifies the technical conditions of the existing procedures for evaluating the energy efficiency of buildings. In this study, a set of standardised profiles characterised by the intended use (tertiary - office), internal load (low, medium, or high), and usage period (8, 12, and 16 hours) has been defined. All spaces are considered conditioned spaces. Buildings with a 24-hour usage period have been omitted as they are not representative of office use.
- **Architecture and Passive Systems:** It is related to the architectural definition of the project and its passive strategies.
- **Active Energy Systems:** It focuses on the technical systems of the building.

Table 1. Summary of the parameters used in the study

Occupancy and Operating Condition Parameters		Architectural and Passive Design Parameters	
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Internal load	Low	Window to wall ratio in southern façades	30% SE
	Medium		60% SE
	High		90% SE
Operating hours	8h	Window to wall ratio in northern façades	30% NO
	12h		60% NO
	16h		90% NO
System Parameters		Thermal envelope	CTE DB HE1 Minimum
IEQ ventilation	Constant		CTE DB HE Appendix E
	CO2 sensor		Improved envelope, g:0,60
Lighting sensor	With lighting sensor	Improved envelope, g:0,30	
	Without lighting sensor	Solar protection (UNE-EN 14501)	Without solar protection
Lighting efficiency	VEEI minimum (5 W/m2)		Fixed exterior minimum effect (0.55)
	VEEI optimised (10 W/m2)		Mobile interior small effect (0.40)
Climate control type	Heat pump	Fixed exterior moderate effect (0.25)	
	District heating & cooling	Mobile exterior large effect (0.15)	
	VRF	Natural ventilation	10 ACH
Less than minimum	5 ACH		
PV production	CTE DB HE		Without natural ventilation
	BCN Code	With thermal mass	
		Thermal mass	Without thermal mass

From the combinations of these parameters, 622,081 scenarios were generated for evaluation. The considerable number of scenarios requires an open energy certification tool with parametric and massive simulation capability. For this reason, the SG-SAVE¹ tool was used, leveraging the platform it was built upon, Open Studio², and its well-established engine, EnergyPlus, to carry out the simulations. This Ministry-recognised tool serves two main functions: verifying compliance with

¹ SGSave - <https://www.efinovatic.es/energyPlus/>

² PAT (Parametric analysis Tool) <https://github.com/NREL/OpenStudio-PAT>

minimum energy performance standards and conducting energy performance certifications. At the same time, it uses dynamic calculations of energy performance that facilitates a detailed representation of all study parameters.

To verify regulatory compliance of the different simulated scenarios, the following indicators were established for compliance with energy requirements:

- DB HE CTE 2019 (CTE). Structured into six mandatory sections, this document addresses energy demand reduction with prescriptive indicators in Section HE1, while Section HE0 focuses on performance-based indicators, such as the primary energy limit (HE0).
- Recast of the 2021 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)

3. Analysis of results: Compliance with EU Directive 2021/0426 (COD) – ZEB vs. nZEB

According to Recast of the 2021 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) the definition of ZEB and nZEB are as follows:

- **ZEB:** zero-emission building means a building with a very high energy performance requiring zero or a very low amount of energy, producing zero on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels and producing zero or a very low amount of operational greenhouse gas emissions. This is the new requirement for building.
- **nZEB:** nearly zero-energy building means a building with a very high energy performance where the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required is covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or energy from renewable sources produced nearby. Any new building that complies with CTE DB HE 2019 is considered nZEB.

Therefore, ZEB is the new standard for buildings when the EU State Members transpose the EU directive in their national codes. In this section an analysis of the compliance according to current codes (nZEB) and the future standard (ZEB) is made.

In Figure 3, the distribution of all simulated scenarios in relation to the combined compliance of the CTE and the potential future Zero Emissions Building (ZEB) indicator is shown. The values represented correspond to the total primary energy consumption ($C_{ep,tot}$). The dashed orange line indicates the simulated cases of each group of results. The percentage number expresses the weight of each group relative to the total simulations.

Figure 3. Distribution of total primary energy consumption and the number of cases based on compliance with the Cep limit for a Zero Emissions Building according to EU 2021/0426 (COD) crossed with compliance with CTE DB HE 2019 (nZEB)

It can be observed that a total of 46% of the simulated scenarios comply with ZEB. 10% of the scenarios comply with ZEB but do not comply with CTE DB HE 2019 (nZEB). This graph clearly shows how a more ambitious indicator in limiting total primary energy consumption ensures buildings with a very low consumption, unlike the CTE DB HE indicators, where, for example, the Cep,tot,lim (total primary energy consumption limit in CTE) indicator is more permissive. Furthermore, the first whisker plot in Figure 3 (i.e., “Does not comply with nZEB” - “Complies with ZEB”) illustrates that the UE 2021/0426 (COD) directive only recommends limitation to total primary energy consumption (Cep,tot) and does not have indicators to control the demand. However, the current regulation does not have performance indicators to limit cooling and heating demand; only prescriptive indicators. Lastly, it should be noted that all simulated scenarios represent buildings that are currently technically, economically, industrially, and commercially viable.

4. Summary of samples in relation to nZEB and ZEB for demand, Cep,nren, and Cep,tot indicators

This section synthesises the compliance of the samples with CTE 2019 (nZEB building) and the EU Directive 2021/0426(COD) (ZEB building). The tool is structured in a matrix based on OOCs, where columns represent internal load levels and rows indicate hours of operation. Once the matrix is segregated by OOCs each graph is read as follows:

- **Distribution matrix of the sample (X = Cep,ren; Y=cooling & heating demand) based on OOCs and compliance with nZEB and ZEB buildings (Figure 4).** A scatter plot where each point represents a scenario and is placed in relation to non-renewable primary energy consumption on the x-axis and cooling & heating demand (heating and cooling) on the y-axis. Each point is coloured according to its level of compliance:
 - Green dot: complies with CTE 2019 (nZEB) and complies with the EU directive (ZEB)
 - Blue dot: complies with CTE 2019 (nZEB) but does not comply with the EU directive (ZEB)
 - Purple dot: does not comply with CTE 2019 (nZEB) but complies with the EU directive (ZEB)
 - Yellow dot: does not comply with CTE 2019 (nZEB) nor the EU directive (ZEB)

For each OOC, the percentage of scenarios (points) for each compliance situation is provided.

- **Distribution matrix of the sample (X = $C_{ep,tot}$; Y=cooling & heating demand) based on OOCs and compliance with nZEB and ZEB buildings** (Figure 5). A scatter plot where each point represents a scenario and is placed in relation to total primary energy consumption on the x-axis and cooling & heating demand (heating and cooling) on the y-axis. Each point is coloured according to its level of compliance:
 - Green dot: complies with CTE 2019 (nZEB)
 - Yellow dot: does not comply with CTE 2019 (nZEB)

Additionally, a vertical dashed line at $70\text{kWh/m}^2 C_{ep,tot}$ indicates compliance with EU Directive 2021/0426(COD) (ZEB building); thus, all scenarios (points) to the left of this line comply with the directive, while those to the right do not comply.

Figure 4. Distribution matrix graph of the 22@ sample (X = Cep,ren; Y = cooling and heating demand) based on COFs and compliance with nZEB and ZEB buildings

Figure 5. Distribution matrix graph of the 22@ sample (X = Cep,tot; Y = cooling and heating demand) based on COFs and compliance with nZEB and ZEB buildings

From these matrices, some general conclusions can be drawn:

- **nZEB Compliance:** There is a clear limitation on non-renewable primary energy consumption as well as a reduction in cooling & heating demand for low-load scenarios. These performance reductions, especially in cooling & heating demands, become blurred as the load level increases, and no clear trend is observed. CTE DB HE 2019 (nZEB) compliance guarantees a building with low demands due to the type of indicators used to control demand, which are prescriptive rather than performance based.
- **ZEB Compliance:** There is a clear tendency to reduce the possibilities of complying with the ZEB building as the internal load level and hours of operation increase, moving from, for example, 78% compliance of nZEB and ZEB in Low-8h to 4% in High-16h.
- There is a tendency for the distribution of points to increase their values on the x-axis (Cep,tot or Cep,nren) as the internal load and hours of use increase. This graph allows us to qualify that hours of operation have a greater impact on increasing primary energy consumption than internal load level, as they are more sparsely distributed on the x-axis with more hours of operation than with higher internal loads.
- The indicator Cep,nren,lim can be identified, as each COF has **two limits** depending on the lighting power VEEI. One limit, which is associated with the VEEI limit scenarios, is more distinguishable than the other, contrary to the limit referring to optimised VEEI which is not as clearly defined.
- The Cep,nren,lim indicator becomes increasingly stringent with longer hours of use, while it is less stringent with higher internal loads. As usage hours increase, the number of non-compliant points based on the Cep,nren,lim value rises, whereas it decreases with a higher internal load. Therefore, it can be confirmed that Cep,nren,lim is more restrictive with 8 hours of operation and low internal load.
- Regarding the prescriptive indicators of CTE 2019 for achieving nZEB compliance, there is a uniform distribution in low load scenarios that limit cooling demand. As internal load increases, the distribution of non-compliant points does not necessarily align with low cooling demand. This is due to prescriptive limitations that may restrict performance optimization.

5. Analysis of results: Evaluation of parameters in different regulatory compliance scenarios

Table 2 provides an overview of 622,081 simulated scenarios, organised into 26 rows and 6 columns. It relates the various parameters defined in building configuration scenarios with selected energy efficiency indicators. The results are expressed as a percentage of compliance for each indicator, according to the parameter.

For example, if you look at the column for compliance with the CTE 2019 (4th column), you can see how, in relation to a lighting sensor, 75% of scenarios with a lighting sensor comply with CTE 2019-nZEB, while only 66% of scenarios without a lighting sensor comply with this regulation. Furthermore, looking at the column for compliance with the global transmittance value K and the parameters of envelope definition, 70% of scenarios with minimal thermal envelope definition according to HE1 (Thermal envelope: CT DB HE1 Minimum) comply, whereas scenarios with closures defined by Appendix E (Thermal Envelope: CTE DB HE Appendix E) of HE1 have a 71% compliance in the Thermal Envelope Kg category.

Table 2. Percentage frequency of cases compliant with each of the indicators mentioned

Percentage of cases that comply and the parameter definition appears		Compliance HEO (Cep,tot,lim - kW-h/m ² -year)	Compliance HEO (Cep,nren,lim (kW-h/m ² -year)	Compliance Qsol;jul	Compliance Kg	Compliance CTE 2019	Compliance EU Directive 2021/0426 (COD)
Lighting sensor	With lighting sensor	100	99	86	84	75	54
	Without lighting sensor	100	88	86	82	66	39
IEQ ventilation	CO2 sensor	100	95	86	84	72	52
	Constant	100	92	86	82	69	42
Thermal mass	With thermal mass	100	94	86	84	71	48
	Without thermal mass	100	93	86	82	69	46
Solar protection	Fixed exterior minimum effect (0.55)	100	93	100	84	79	46
	Fixed exterior moderate effect (0.25)	100	95	100	86	82	48
	Mobile exterior large effect (0.15)	100	95	100	86	82	49
	Mobile interior small effect (0.40)	100	93	78	82	65	46
	Without solar protection	100	92	53	77	45	45
Natural ventilation	10 ACH	100	96	86	90	76	53
	5 ACH	100	96	86	88	75	51
	Without natural ventilation	100	89	86	72	60	36
Lighting efficiency	VEEI minimum (10 W/m ²)	100	88	86	82	65	26
	VEEI optimised (5 W/m ²)	100	99	86	84	75	68
Thermal envelope	CTE DB HE Appendix E	100	94	80	71	58	48
	Improved envelope, g = 0.3	100	94	100	96	90	46
	Improved envelope, g = 0.6	100	93	84	95	77	47
	CTE DB HE1 Minimum	100	94	80	70	57	47
WWR NO	30% NO	100	94	95	86	78	47
	60% NO	100	94	85	85	71	47
	90% NO	100	93	78	77	62	47
WWR SE	30% SE	100	93	97	100	90	45
	60% SE	100	94	87	80	68	48
	90% SE	100	94	75	69	53	48

5.1 Analysis by columns

- **HE0 Cep,tot,lim:** All scenarios comply with the limit of total primary energy consumption of HE0 according to the CTE.
- **HE0 Cep,nren,lim:** There are scenarios that do not comply with the limit of renewable primary energy consumption according to HE0, especially those with high VEEI lighting, those without an illumination sensor, and those without natural ventilation.
- **Qsol;jul:** Compliance with the Qsol indicator, which limits the amount of solar radiation in July, is strongly associated with the architectural parameters of window elements and solar protection.
- **Global Thermal Transmittance: K limit:** Compliance with the K limit indicator varies based on envelope thermal quality parameters and natural ventilation, which significantly reduces cooling demand and puts a limitation to that prescriptive parameter.
- **CTE 2019 - nZEB:** Compliance with this global indicator is 67%, with cases of non-compliance mostly due to the absence of solar protection and excess window proportion. The use of natural ventilation and optimised VEEI lighting solutions significantly improve compliance.
- **European Directive EPBD Recast - ZEB:** Compliance with the future European directive is at 47%, considering a total primary energy consumption limit of 70 kWh/m²·a. The compliance trend by parameters is very similar to those of the current nZEB regulation.

5.2 Analysis of results: Best-case scenario

The best-case scenario that can be achieved considering the parameters, which are based on realistic and feasible application of passive and active energy efficiency strategies in the context of Barcelona, was elected based on the medium scenario, i.e., based on a 12-hour occupancy profile and medium internal load intensity for geometry type 22@. The lowest demand and consumption were found in the same case; with lighting sensor and high lighting efficiency, CO₂ sensor to optimise ventilation, high thermal mass, natural ventilation, an improved thermal envelope with a g-value of 0.6 combined with an adjustable, efficient exterior solar shading, a window-to-wall ratio of 60% towards the north and 30% towards the south, using a VRF-system and maximizing PV production. This configuration has a combined cooling and heating demand of 3.7 kWh/m²·yr, a total primary energy use of 39.9 kWh/m²·yr, and a non-renewable energy use of 32.9 kWh/m²·yr. This complies with all regulations included in this study and corresponds to an EPC-rating (Gobierno de España, 2015) of A for cooling and heating respectively.

6. Conclusions

From the analysis presented, the main conclusions regarding the implications of current regulations for new office buildings can be summarised as follows:

- The HE0 basic requirements of CTE-HE 2019 are not very ambitious, and practically all scenarios comply with the limits of total primary energy consumption. In contrast, the limits imposed by HE1 are more restrictive, however, since they are prescriptive rather than performance-based limits, there are some situations where buildings, despite having good or even desirable performance in terms of primary energy consumption, do not comply with this section.
- The change from a performance-based approach to a prescriptive approach in the HE1 criteria has reduced the influence of the CTE (Spanish Construction Code) on the environmental performance of buildings.
- It is necessary to reduce the HE0 primary energy consumption limit. Many viable scenarios could easily be below the sub-70 kWh/m² values proposed for the ZEB directive in the EPBD Recast, suggesting a potential for higher municipal regulatory requirements.
- The differentiation of primary energy consumption limits based on the intensity of use of the building and the standardization of initial conditions for new office buildings at the municipal level is advisable.
- There are configurations of office building desirable in terms of easily achieving nZEB and ZEB requirements.
 - Reducing internal loads with lighting efficiency and control
 - Reducing solar gains with high efficiency solar protection
 - Free cooling using natural ventilation
- The best case for a medium scenario performs significantly better than any of the planned or existing building regulations in Barcelona, suggesting that the strategies applicable and feasible today are more than adequate in terms of compliance.

The methodology developed for this study can be replicated for existing buildings (Figure 6), identifying the necessary conditions to transform the current built environment into one that meets climate neutrality objectives without exhausting the available carbon budget.

Figure 6. General methodology, adjusted and applied on a potential future study on existing buildings

In the case of applying the methodology to existing buildings, more emphasis should be placed on the initial analysis and definition of parameters (see Figure 6). This schematic diagram is a modification of the current methodology focusing on the changes that should be applied in an existing building analysis. The manual analysis of areas of interest could be extended to include urban fabric types, and in parallel, a data analysis of existing EPCs could provide more information regarding tendencies of building characteristics, energy performance and system use. This would provide a comprehensive picture of the current building stock and together with research on renovation packages and related policies determine feasible future enhancement scenarios.

The initial analysis is used to refine the scope and ensure that the results can be used as a reliable basis of decision making and that the number of scenarios is limited enough for the study to be completed within a reasonable timeframe. The rest of the process is similar, adjusting the parametrization to revolve around renovation packages instead of individual measures to enhance the potential for implementation in real life practice whilst reducing simulation time.

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Appendix A: Detailed methodological framework

1. Identification of building types and reference geometries

2. Parametrisation and simulation of scenarios

3. Post-processing of results and extraction of indicators

Towards sustainable construction for deep renovation: a comprehensive analysis of the transition from cost-optimal methodology to multi-objective methodology

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Keywords: Multi-Objective Cost Optimization, Cost-optimal methodology, Deep Retrofit, Energy Efficiency, Building Decarbonization, Life Cycle Assessment, Social Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cost Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

1. Introduction

The construction sector is the second-largest source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with buildings accounting for 30% of global energy consumption due to their operational energy use (Laxmi Haigh, et al., 2021; European Commission, n.d.-a; International Energy Agency, n.d.). Given this context, it represents a crucial area for advancing sustainable practices to mitigate climate change. In recent years, there has been a growing focus on sustainable building development (UNEP, n.d.; Khan et al., 2019), largely driven by the European Commission (EC) through initiatives like the European Green Deal (European Commission, n.d.-b). To address climate change, the EC has introduced various measures and policies, including a new recast of Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (Zangheri et al., 2021; Renovate Europe, n.d.) and the Renovation Wave Strategy (European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, n.d.).

In line with these goals, Member States (MS) have been working to meet the targets set by the 2018 EPBD, including requirements for nearly zero-energy buildings (nZEB), which specifies minimum energy performance for both new and existing buildings. The updated EPBD 2024/1275 (EUR-Lex, 2024) now requires all new buildings be zero-emission (ZEB) by 2030, with existing buildings expected to reach ZEB standards by 2050. To support these performance targets, the Directive promotes a cost-optimal approach that balances investment with energy savings over the building's life cycle. Additionally, Annex VII of the EPBD outlines a comparative methodology to determine cost-optimal levels for buildings.

The “cost-optimal level” is defined as the energy performance level that results in the lowest cost over a building's estimated economic life cycle, encompassing energy-related investment, maintenance, and operating expenses. Each Member State (MS) determines this economic life cycle, applying it to buildings or building elements where energy performance standards are set. The methodology also distinguishes between new and existing buildings, as well as for different building categories. A key challenge is defining a Reference Building (RB) to establish these benchmarks, given the diversity of Europe's building stock—a task assigned to each MS. Establishing the RB is essential for setting accurate cost-optimal standards (TABULA project, n.d.; ASIEPI, n.d.; Corgnati, et al., 2013).

Although the terms “cost-effective” and “cost-optimal” are often used interchangeably in energy performance discussions, they have distinct meanings. “Cost-effective” refers to situations where the total cost of implementing measures is outweighed by the benefits they provide over their lifespan. This calculation contemplates both the initial investment and the savings generated. If the overall result is positive, the measure is considered “cost-effective” (Atanasiu et al., 2013). On the other

hand, "cost-optimal" refers to the solution or combination of solutions that maximises the net present value, meaning the approach that yields the greatest financial benefit.

However, the current energy renovation rate is only 1% per year, significantly below the 3% target set by the Renovation Wave Strategy (Dulian, 2024; EUR-Lex, 2020; Sibileau, 2021). Increasing this rate is particularly challenging in vulnerable neighbourhoods, where financial constraints pose a significant barrier (Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015; Ricci et al., 2024). Acknowledging the economic impact of large-scale renovation across the existing building stock, the NextGeneration EU programme (European Union, n.d.-c) was introduced as a financial mechanism to support a triple transition: socioeconomic, digital, and ecological within the EU European Union.

There is scientific evidence supporting the concept of "deep renovation." However, organizations such as the Global Building Performance Network (GBPN) and the Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE) highlight the fact that the definition of Deep Renovation (DR) varies across regions and globally, and this may lead to confusion (Joyce et al., 2013). The EPBD 2021 recast provided a common definition for DR, describing it as a renovation aligned with the "energy efficiency first" principle. It focuses on key building elements and aims to transform a building or unit to: (a) nearly zero-energy by January 1, 2030 and (b) zero-emission from January 1, 2030 onward. However, DR not only seeks optimal energy reduction but also ensures a healthy indoor environment and contributes to neighbourhood improvements (Mutani & Todeschi, 2018; Freed & Felder, 2017; Fawcett & Killip, 2019). Recent studies by one of the authors have shown that when users are informed about the co-benefits of DR, they are more likely to undertake such investments despite the financial challenges involved (Crespo Sánchez, et al., 2021).

The importance of developing a "Long-term Renovation Strategy" was already highlighted in Directive 2018/844/EU, Article 2a. This strategy aims to identify cost-effective renovation approaches tailored to specific building types and climatic zones, while also considering significant trigger points in the building's life cycle (EUR-Lex, 2018). Figure 1 shows the evolution of the various legislations over the years.

Deep Renovation of the existing public building stock is a key strategy for ensuring compliance with EU Directives and tackling related challenges. Recent research has increasingly focused on the CO₂ emissions associated to embodied energy in buildings, considering not only during their operational phase but also stages such as manufacturing, construction, and demolition. Studies, such as those by Kertsmik et al. (2023), highlight the shift towards CO₂ optimization, rather than solely focusing on operational energy efficiency, aligning with the main objective of the EPBD.

Figure 1. Context of the European Legislation over years. Source: Own elaboration based on the cited bibliography

This research aims to address emerging challenges in sustainable construction development. While most mitigation strategies for deep renovation (DR) focus on reducing operational energy in buildings, the primary objective of this study is twofold. First, it provides a holistic overview of various sustainable assessments methodologies, including environmental, social and economic impacts. Second, it identifies the challenges and propose solutions to help achieve the EU’s decarbonization targets for the construction sector, promoting a more sustainable construction.

2. Methodology

This research should be viewed as a continuation of previous studies by Crespo et al., specifically their publication “Architectural and Environmental Strategies Towards a Cost-Optimal Deep Energy Retrofit for Mediterranean Public High Schools” (Crespo Sánchez, et al., 2023). In this work, a methodology was developed to quantitatively address the energy challenges faced by school buildings in a Mediterranean climate zone in Spain.

The methodology for the present study is divided into two major phases (Figure 2). The first involves a preliminary evaluation of the results from the aforementioned research, with a focus on economic and environmental aspects. The second phase consists of a comprehensive literature review of existing research and European regulatory frameworks, aimed at identifying current trends and strategies to promote more sustainable construction practices.

Figure 2. Methodology overview. Source: Own elaboration

2.1 Phase 1: Preliminary results evaluation

This phase presents an enhanced methodology aimed at addressing the challenge of energy retrofitting in schools located in Catalonia, a region with a Mediterranean climate. The study specifically focuses on eight school buildings managed by the Departament d’Ensenyament de la Generalitat de Catalunya. The methodology is divided into two sub-phases:

- Phase 1.1 involves identifying opportunities by ranking buildings based on energy demand and CO₂ emissions, assessing baseline energy scenarios, and examining unique building characteristics to develop replicable retrofit strategies.
- Phase 1.2 focuses on prioritizing energy improvements using cost-optimal criteria, developing renovation strategies aligned with nZEB standards, conducting life cycle analysis to evaluate environmental impacts, and balancing investment costs with energy savings to ensure economically viable deep energy renovations.

2.2 Phase 2: Systematic literature review for sustainable construction

Building on the findings from the experimental demonstration in the case study, this phase focuses on evaluating the social dimension, which is essential for achieving the renovation rates necessary to address the climate emergency. It includes a thorough review of existing literature, EU directives, and innovative business models aimed at promoting deep energy renovation and improving energy efficiency in the building sector. In this context, the proposed methodology adopts a multi-objective approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic impacts to inform decision making.

3. Case study and results

Eight schools, typically constructed in the 1970s, were evaluated in this research. These buildings suffer from poor thermal and air quality, particularly during the summer when overheating becomes a major issue. Currently, they lack active cooling systems and domestic hot water demand, with lighting improvements managed through annual budgets by the school board. The economic context was considered in developing a realistic energy action model aligned with the Catalan public administration.

The second phase targets the building prioritised in the initial assessment, located in the Köppen climatic zone Cfa (Zone D3 according to the Spanish Technical Building Code). Life cycle analysis (LCA) was used to evaluate the environmental impact of deep renovation strategies, with a particular

emphasis on embedded CO₂ emissions. The findings reveal that enhancing façade thermal conductivity reduces heating demand by 40%, but increases cooling demand by 10%. The external insulation (ETICS) option does not adequately offset its environmental impacts across phases A1-5 and C1-4. Improving heating systems is critical, as they account for half of CO₂ emissions. Switching from diesel to a gas condensation system can reduce emissions by 26%, while a biomass boiler achieves A-level certification, has four times the environmental impact of gas. The payback period is 14 years for biomass and 11.5 years for gas.

To improve energy certification by two levels without biomass, integrating renewable sources is essential. A self-consumption of 40,000 kWh/year can achieve this without replacing the boiler, or 11,000 kWh/year with replacement, aligning with nZEB standards and offering a payback of 13 years. While photovoltaic systems initially increase environmental impact, they quickly offset this during their operational phase, resulting in favourable lifecycle performance.

Strategic interventions focus on solar protection to manage cooling demands and prevent overheating in the absence of active cooling systems, all while maintaining low environmental impacts. However, the methodology faces challenges due to fluctuating energy prices, such as the recent rise in natural gas costs, which can impact the effectiveness of various measures.

4. Demonstrative assessment of the multi-objective approach

The current cost-optimal methodology mainly emphasises the operational phase of buildings, often overlooking the environmental impacts of construction and end-of-life stages. Recent scientific advancements advocate for a multi-objective approach that includes cost-optimal evaluation, passive improvement strategies for zero-energy buildings (ZEBs), and circularity models to reduce resource consumption and embodied carbon emissions. Given that the residential sector represents the largest portion of the built environment, it is crucial to also consider social impacts. As such, a comprehensive energy assessment methodology should integrate environmental, social, and economic factors for sustainable retrofits (Crespo Sánchez et al., 2023).

The following subsections delve into the core pillars of this multi-objective approach: Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA), which evaluates the environmental footprint of a building across its entire life cycle; Life Cycle Cost Assessment (LCC), which provides a financial perspective on long-term sustainability; and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), which examines the social implications and benefits associated with building practices.

4.1 Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA)

- E-LCA evaluates a building's environmental impacts from a comprehensive life cycle perspective, covering stages such as raw material extraction, manufacturing, construction, use, and end-of-life.
- The principles of E-LCA are outlined in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, with additional definitions provided by European standards like EN 15978.
- Studies, such as those by Bovea and Powell (2016) show a growing interest in using E-LCA to assess the environmental performance of construction and demolition, paralleling the evolving legal framework, such as the introduction of Level(s). Other studies suggest that reducing energy in the operational phase is leading to increased attention on optimizing the entire building life cycle (Citherlet & Defaux, 2007), while some have noted that certain materials, such as wood, have a lower environmental impact in their production phase compared to other materials (Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010).

4.2 Life Cycle Cost Assessment (LCC)

- LCC focuses on the total costs associated with a building throughout its life cycle, providing insights into the long-term economic sustainability of construction projects.
- The European Union has incorporated LCC into public tender evaluations through Directive 2014/24/EU, emphasizing cost control throughout all building phases.
- Recent studies have started to adopt a combined environmental and economic perspective across the entire building life cycle, considering the impacts of LCA during phases A1-A5 and C1-C4 (Verbeeck & Hens, 2010; Caruso et al., 2021).

4.3 Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)

- S-LCA evaluates the social impacts of products or services throughout their life cycles, aiming to enhance the social performance of organizations and stakeholders by using social and socio-economic data for decision-making. Its methodology is defined in the UNEP/SETAC guidelines (Benoît Norris et al., 2022).
- Common challenges in S-LCA include measurement quality, scoring methods, data availability, and the emphasis on materials rather than construction processes.
- Recent studies highlight the importance of measuring social impacts related to user comfort and health, and extrapolating these effects to broader socio-economic outcomes, such as public health investments, income levels, and labour absenteeism (Pomianowski et al., 2023).

5. Discussion and conclusion

Despite the EU's efforts, there is still much to be done if the European built environment is to be fully decarbonised and sustainable by 2050. Key issues requiring attention include:

1. **Unification of main guidelines:** There is a need to clarify key concepts, as confusion remains within the scientific community regarding the varying interpretations of commonly used terms. This includes the fundamental definitions of cost-optimal methodology and cost-effectiveness, as well as concepts related to LCA and nZEB.
2. **Expansion beyond the operational phase to a whole life cycle:** One of the primary challenges with the cost-optimal methodology is the diversity of Europe's built environment, which varies in climate zones, building types, and usage patterns. The current definition of the reference building (RB) is seen as a weak point. Greater focus should be placed on the RB for Deep Renovation, especially given the large number of buildings with poor energy efficiency. It is important to focus on existing buildings, rather than relying on a generalised reference model. This approach should involve using actual buildings as references, incorporating energy bills and simulations and conducting a comprehensive energy audit.
3. **A transition towards a more sustainable Europe.** To effectively transition to a circular economy model, it is essential to fully embrace the concept and assign economic value to material recovery, not just environmental benefits. Introducing fees or tolls in projects could further emphasise the importance of this shift. Additionally, materials used in renovations should be regarded as valuable assets with long-term worth.

In summary, this work underscores the necessity of addressing both operational and embodied energy in buildings through a comprehensive methodology that combines cost optimization with multi-objective considerations. It highlights the integration of various sustainable assessment methodologies—encompassing environmental, social, and economic impacts—while identifying key challenges and proposing solutions to meet the EU’s decarbonization targets in the construction sector. Initiatives like Zero Energy Renovation Kits are crucial to advancing the Renovation Wave. Additionally, recent EU-funded research indicates growing interest in off-site and multifunctional construction technologies, especially in building envelopes.

The findings emphasise that focusing solely on CO₂ emissions is insufficient; it is equally important to consider the impacts on resources and waste, which are increasingly significant in European policies. Therefore, achieving decarbonization requires two interconnected strategies: a thorough analysis of passive strategies for zero operational emissions and the adoption of a circular economy to attain zero embodied carbon emissions and waste. These efforts must be supported by unified criteria and methodologies under a regulatory EU framework.

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iBRoad2EPC: Simplified renovation passport

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Keywords: Renovation Passport, Decarbonization, Energy Efficiency, Energy Performance Certificate, EPBD, NZEBs, Deep Renovation

1. Introduction

In the face of urgent global climate goals, societies worldwide must eliminate carbon dependency, and achieving this transition is essential. The construction sector, which accounts for approximately 39% of energy consumption and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions within the European Union (Green Building Council, 2021) has a critical role to play in this shift. Decarbonizing the construction industry is thus one of the project's central aims and starting points.

A key factor in this sector's carbon footprint is the existing building stock. According to Spain's National Institute of Statistics (INE), 87% of the buildings that will exist in 2050 have already been constructed. In Spain alone, 44% of homes were built before 1979, prior to the implementation of energy efficiency regulations. This indicates that a significant portion of current buildings lacks the structural and energy-efficiency standards needed for a sustainable future. Given these statistics, renovating existing buildings is indispensable to achieving decarbonization in the construction sector. The Spanish National Renovation Strategy (ERESEE) (Ministry of Transport, Mobility and the Urban Agenda, 2020) has set a target to renovate 300,000 homes annually, yet progress is currently limited to just 30,000, underscoring the need to increase the rate of renovations tenfold.

The revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) in the European Union supports the goal of a highly efficient and decarbonised building stock by 2050. This directive mandates transforming most existing buildings from energy-inefficient structures into nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEBs), with deep renovations offering substantial potential for energy savings and emissions reduction. However, this objective faces multiple obstacles, particularly the complexity and cost of comprehensive renovation projects. Many building owners lack knowledge about which measures to implement or in what order, leading to hesitancy and delays in taking action. Several factors contribute to the slow pace of renovation. Comprehensive building renovation is a complex, long-term commitment that requires careful planning, coordination, and financial investment. For example, although energy efficiency certificates provide a snapshot of a building's energy status and potential improvements, many homeowner communities cannot afford the significant upfront costs needed for large-scale renovation projects. Additionally, while phased renovations over time may seem practical, they often lack the strategic, comprehensive perspective necessary for maximum impact.

To address this, new tools such as the Renovation Passport and the Existing Building Book have been developed to support long-term renovation planning. These tools expand on the function of energy efficiency certificates by including phased renovation plans aimed at achieving decarbonised buildings. However, despite the value they offer, these documents are often technical and complex, making them difficult for non-experts to interpret.

This is where iBRoad2EPC comes in as an innovative support tool within this project. Designed to simplify the renovation process, iBRoad2EPC offers a user-friendly approach that aids building owners in planning and implementing effective, phased renovations with a clear pathway toward decarbonization.

2. iBRoad2EPC project

Launched in 2021, iBRoad2EPC¹ is a European initiative funded under the Horizon 2020 programme. Its primary goal is to integrate the Building Renovation Passport with the Energy Efficiency Certificate, providing a comprehensive tool to streamline deep renovations across Europe. Building on the foundation laid by its predecessor, the iBRoad project (2017-2020), which developed a model for the Building Renovation Passport, iBRoad2EPC focuses on advancing personalised, phased renovation planning to help building owners achieve substantial energy savings and decarbonization (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual scheme. Source: iBRoad Project

iBRoad2EPC takes the concept a step further by connecting the Building Renovation Passport with energy certification data to create a more dynamic and actionable tool. The project’s core innovation is a user-friendly assistant designed to visualise the potential improvements a building can achieve through various phases of renovation, using insights drawn from the building’s Energy Efficiency Certificate. This approach allows building owners to make informed decisions, evaluating each stage’s impact on energy performance and overall efficiency.

To validate and refine the tool, iBRoad2EPC conducted a testing phase across six European countries: Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Romania, and Spain. In each country, 10 experienced building certification technicians applied the tool in real-world settings and provided feedback based on their observations. This iterative process has enabled the project team to fine-tune the assistant based on actual user interactions and outcomes, ensuring the tool is practical and adaptable to diverse building contexts.

¹ iBRoad2EPC Project <https://gbce.es/proyectos/ibroad2epc/>

The project’s objectives in each participating country include the following:

- **Contextual analysis:** Identifying each country’s unique needs, challenges, criteria, and opportunities to optimise the iBRoad2EPC methodology.
- **Preparation for national implementation:** Establishing a foundation for widespread adoption by aligning the tool with each country’s regulatory and market frameworks.
- **Testing and evaluation:** Demonstrating and assessing the tool’s effectiveness to ensure it meets its objectives.
- **Guidance development:** Producing an integration guide based on insights gained during the testing phase to support the tool’s use across Europe.

Each country has also established a National Advisory Committee (NAC), comprising experts who provide critical feedback on the tool’s conceptualization, development, and testing. These advisory committees ensure that iBRoad2EPC is compatible with existing national certification systems, laying the groundwork for its long-term integration into national energy policies and standards. Through these collaborative efforts, iBRoad2EPC aims to become an indispensable resource in the drive toward decarbonised, energy-efficient buildings across Europe.

3. iBRoad2EPC assistant

The culmination of the iBRoad2EPC project is an innovative energy consulting tool that provides building owners with a comprehensive, phased roadmap toward achieving climate neutrality (Figure 2). Developed for use by construction professionals, this tool –named after the project itself, iBRoad2EPC– outlines a strategic rehabilitation plan, allowing building owners to approach climate-neutrality through either a complete renovation in a single step or multiple, coordinated phases. The phased approach enables each step to build on the previous one, facilitating advanced preparation for future stages and incorporating future regulatory or technical obligations.

Figure 2. Wizard display. Source: iBRoad2EPC Project

Serving as a bridge between existing Energy Efficiency Certificates (EEC) and Building Renovation Passports (BRP), iBRoad2EPC combines the short-term insights of EECs with the long-term perspective offered by BRPs. BRPs are tailored roadmaps that provide a sequence of recommended interventions, guiding building owners through a gradual process to achieve comprehensive energy improvements. By integrating BRP elements into existing EEC frameworks, iBRoad2EPC expands on current certification systems, enriching them with a long-term decarbonization goal.

The iBRoad2EPC tool’s decarbonization roadmap addresses several specific objectives:

- **Sequence optimization:** Including renovation measures in an optimised sequence to prevent poor investments and avoid “lock-in” effects that limit future improvement potential.
- **Comprehensive strategy alignment:** Ensuring that each implemented measure aligns with an overarching rehabilitation plan.
- **Regulatory and financial compliance:** Preparing buildings to meet anticipated regulations, such as mandatory minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) and EU taxonomy guidelines.
- **User-friendly presentation:** Presenting information clearly for non-technical users to understand and act upon.
- The iBRoad2EPC is structured as an online document and is composed of three main sections:
- **Visualization of the rehabilitation strategy:** An overview of the proposed sequence of renovations.
- **Detailed rehabilitation steps:** Specific measures recommended for each phase.
- **Energy savings tips:** Practical advice for achieving additional energy savings

Enfoque modular

Figure 3. Modular approach to the wizard. Source: iBRoad2EPC project

The tool employs a modular approach (Figure 3), with a basic module that can be extended by additional modules focusing on energy, costs, Smart Readiness Indicators, and accessibility features. Though not a calculation tool, iBRoad2EPC acts as a planning, organization, and visualization platform, requiring a few preliminary setup steps before use. It simplifies the process for auditors, allowing them to easily assign rehabilitation measures, overwrite preconfigured content, and adapt the information for building owners.

The central function of iBRoad2EPC is the definition of a customised rehabilitation strategy, which auditors craft based on key building characteristics, such as:

- The choice between complete or phased rehabilitation
- The age and condition of existing systems and components
- The optimal sequence of renovation measures
- The need for compatible systems
- Compliance with future regulatory obligations

Once all data is entered into the iBRoad2EPC assistant –either manually or by linking it to the building’s EEC file– the strategy is created to guide the building toward a climate-neutral status by the target year. Upon completion, the iBRoad2EPC assistant generates a downloadable document that complements the building’s initial energy certificate. A QR code is added at the end of this document, directing users to the online version for easy access and future reference (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Result display. Source: iBRoad2EPC project

Through this visualization and detailed step-by-step guidance, iBRoad2EPC provides building owners with a practical, actionable path toward sustainable and energy-efficient building operations (Figures 5, 6).

Figures 5, 6. iBRoad2EPC appearance

4. Conclusions

The iBRoad2EPC assistant offers several substantial benefits, marking it as a valuable tool for advancing the EU's goal of achieving a climate-neutral building stock by 2050:

- **Enhanced communication of technical concepts:** A key advantage of iBRoad2EPC is its ability to translate complex technical information into an accessible, user-friendly format. This feature allows non-professional stakeholders to participate meaningfully in the decision-making process for building rehabilitation. For instance, during a community meeting, building owners and residents can easily understand and discuss the phased rehabilitation strategy for their building, thanks to the assistant's visual and straightforward presentation.
- **Improved and cohesive rehabilitation recommendations:** iBRoad2EPC provides more comprehensive and coherent rehabilitation recommendations than traditional Energy Efficiency Certificates (EEC), primarily due to its integration of the Building Renovation Passport (BRP). The assistant designs a long-term, stepwise rehabilitation strategy that organises interventions into a cohesive sequence, avoiding costly errors or redundancies by preparing for future rehabilitation steps in advance.
- **Proactive alignment with future regulatory standards:** One of the assistant's most significant advantages is its ability to inform building owners of upcoming legal requirements, allowing them to plan with regulatory compliance in mind. iBRoad2EPC displays these future obligations on a timeline, enabling auditors to recommend measures that align with national and EU standards. This includes compliance with anticipated regulations, such as minimum energy performance standards (MEPS), fossil fuel phase-out requirements, and enhanced efficiency mandates, which are critical for ensuring a legally compliant path to decarbonization.

The urgency of these improvements is underscored by the EU's "Fit-for-55" package, which mandates a climate-neutral building stock across the EU by 2050. Although 2050 may seem distant, the long-life EPBD (European Commission, 2024) cycles of building components (20 to over 50 years) highlight the need for immediate, strategically sound decisions. The wrong rehabilitation choices made today could require expensive corrections well before the components' end of life. In response, many EU member states have introduced regulatory frameworks designed to support the transition to climate-neutral buildings, smoothing the path toward compliance.

The proposed updates to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) further emphasise this transition, setting intermediate milestones for building performance by specific deadlines. These MEPS act as critical checkpoints, enabling building owners to gradually align with long-term energy and climate goals. The iBRoad2EPC assistant empowers building owners by making them aware of these future standards, allowing them to prepare their buildings proactively and avoid costly retrofits down the line.

Overall, the iBRoad2EPC assistant represents a forward-thinking approach to building rehabilitation, aligning current actions with future goals to create a clear, actionable path toward a sustainable and compliant building sector.

Figure 7. Example of future MEPS wizard compliance. Source: iBRoad2EPC project

5. Next steps

To effectively integrate iBRoad2EPC within national and EU-level frameworks, the next steps should focus on leveraging its strengths and aligning it with existing regulatory and practical needs (Figure 7). Key possibilities for further development include:

- **Integration with certification programmes:** Embedding iBRoad2EPC within existing energy certification programmes would enable users to visualise the progress of each rehabilitation step, supporting a phased approach to achieving energy efficiency.
- **Enhancement as a communication tool for residents and owners:** iBRoad2EPC is designed to present long-term, step-by-step renovation strategies in a clear and accessible format, making it an invaluable tool for residents and building owners.
- **Alignment with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD):** The iBRoad2EPC tool closely aligns with Article 12 of the EPBD, which encourages member states to create a complementary tool allowing building owners to simulate a renovation passport draft and update it following renovations or component replacements.

By focusing on these next steps, iBRoad2EPC can serve as a crucial tool for advancing sustainable building practices, engaging stakeholders at all levels, and supporting regulatory goals for a climate-neutral building stock across the EU.

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Integrating Renovation Passport elements to the Greek Energy Performance Certificate: The Benaki Museum case study

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1. Introduction

While roughly 75% of European buildings are considered inefficient energy-wise, while up to 97% have a significant potential for further improvement (European Commission, 2020, February 17). Following the COVID-19 pandemic, energy efficiency investments hold increased value for economic recovery (Karakosta et al., 2021). To pursue the dual ambition of energy gains and economic growth, the Commission published the strategy “A Renovation Wave for Europe—Greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives” in 2020, along with an action plan and a document presenting available EU funding (EUR-Lex, 2020). The Renovation Wave strategy aims to boost building renovation for climate neutrality and recovery. The objective is to at least double the annual energy renovation rate of buildings by 2030 and to foster deep energy renovations.

Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are already a key instrument of the EU’s building policy and their role as key instrument to foster deep building renovation has been strengthened with the latest recast of the European Performance of Buildings Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/1275 EPBD recast Directive) (EUR-Lex, 2024) which came into effect on 28 May 2024 with a foreseen obligation for Member States to incorporate its requirements into their national laws until 29 May 2026. The Directive is a cornerstone of the EU’s efforts to transition away from fossil fuels by doubling the rate of energy efficiency improvements and tripling renewable energy capacity by 2030, in line with the “Fit for 55” package (Council of the European Union webpage, n.d.) which foresees a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

The recast EPBD introduced a unified approach to EPC rating scales while also modifying existing provisions. Key updates include setting a new standard for new buildings that incorporates a whole-life carbon emissions approach, establishing Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPs) to renovate the worst-performing non-residential buildings, and mandating a progressive renovation trajectory for the residential sector. Additional measures include stringent national building renovation plans, provisions to decarbonise heating and cooling, improved Energy Performance Certificates, an EU framework for Renovation Passports, and a stronger role for one-stop shops. The recast also emphasises a more strategic financial framework, greater social fairness in both mandatory requirements and incentives, and a more impactful approach overall (Buildings Performance Institute Europe, 2024).

According to Article 2 of the 2024 recast EPBD, a Renovation Passport is defined as a tailored roadmap for the deep renovation of a specific building in a maximum number of steps that will significantly improve its energy performance. It is also foreseen that Renovation Passports will provide a clear roadmap for phased renovation over the lifetime of a building, helping owners and investors plan the best timing and scope for interventions.

In Greece, although some steps have been taken to reduce the energy consumption of residential and non-residential buildings through national energy efficiency schemes, the existing building stock still holds significant potential for energy efficiency improvements (Karakosta & Papapostolou, 2023). Architecturally significant buildings protected under conservation laws pose unique challenges for deep renovation, necessitating the development of a comprehensive renovation roadmap by an energy expert to implement appropriate measures. As a case study, the preparation of a Renovation Passport for the energy upgrade of the Benaki Museum in Athens, Greece, is presented, utilizing the tools and methodology developed by the EU-funded iBRoad2EPC project.

2. Methodology

2.1 The iBRoad2EPC Renovation Passport concept and tools

iBRoad2EPC¹ is a European project funded by the Horizon2020 scheme, aiming to improve the reliability, usefulness, and effectiveness of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). The project seeks to establish the next generation of EPCs to support Europe's decarbonisation goals as outlined in the Renovation Wave Strategy, while also enhancing conditions for building occupants (iBRoad2EPC project consortium, 2024). iBRoad2EPC builds upon the iBRoad project (2017-2020), which developed, tested, and delivered a model for the Building Renovation Passport to provide single-family homeowners with personalised advice for stepwise deep renovation of their buildings. Its goal is to bridge the building Renovation Passport with the EPC, expanding their scope to include additional features such as indoor environment and smart technologies, and making them applicable to both residential and public buildings.

iBRoad2EPC is designed with a flexible, modular structure centred on a Basic Module that provides staged deep renovation advice as its core output. Additional features can be integrated into the Renovation Passport through optional add-on modules, including the Investment Cost module, Energy Demand module, Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) module, Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) module, and Measured Energy Performance Indicator (MEPI) module. A user-friendly web interface, referred to as the Assistant, guides energy professionals through the data entry and editing process, ensuring the production of a standardised online output document. (Figure 1).

¹ <https://ibroad2epc.eu/>

The screenshot displays the 'COMPLETE PROJECT DETAILS' form in the iBRoad2EPC Assistant. The form is organized into two columns and includes the following fields:

- Name ***: Text input field.
- Client number**: Text input field with value '111'.
- Building constructed in**: Dropdown menu with value '1990'.
- Country ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Portugal'.
- Climate zone ***: Dropdown menu with value 'I1 VI'.
- Current energy class ***: Dropdown menu with value 'F'.
- Building type ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Residential building'.
- Building sub type ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Multi-family building'.
- Environment ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Urban'.
- Tenure status ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Rented'.
- Heating system constructed in**: Dropdown menu with value '1990'.
- Cooling system constructed in**: Dropdown menu with value '1990'.
- Project trigger ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Extension'.
- Project receiver ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Owner'.
- Recommendations target ***: Dropdown menu with value 'Building owner'.
- Image ***: File upload field with text 'Durchsuchen... Keine Datei ausgewählt.'.
- Previous epc ***: File upload field with text 'Durchsuchen... Keine Datei ausgewählt.'.

A 'Confirm details' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 1. iBRoad2EPC Assistant Standard Front End: input mask for project details

Pre-filled (yet editable) measure suggestion texts make iBRoad2EPC highly time-efficient for energy experts. Through the integration of future regulatory requirements at each renovation phase, building owners receive high-quality recommendations that align with the deep renovation concept and National Building Renovation Plan. Additionally, preparation measures for future renovation stages are automatically generated from the measures database, helping to avoid lock-in effects, extra costs, and ensuring the maximum effectiveness of the renovation works. The Renovation Passport can be issued as an attachment to the EPC or as an additional online document accessible via URL or QR code (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Output variants of iBRoad2EPC as online or printed version (pdf)

More information on the iBRoad2EPC concept and methodology is available on the project report “iBRoad2EPC in depth” (iBRoad2EPC project consortium, 2023).

2.2 The Benaki Museum building

The Benaki Museum building in Athens was one of sixteen public buildings evaluated during the iBRoad2EPC project's field activities in Greece. The Museum was founded in 1930, and it is considered one of the leading cultural organisations in Greece, with over 100,000 exhibits of Greek history and culture. Since 2000, its collections have been separated thematically using regional museums. It is a Private Law Foundation and is considered the oldest museum organisation in Greece (Benaki Museum, 2019).

The main building of the Benaki Museum is housed in the neoclassical mansion of the Benaki family, which was built in 1867-1868 for the merchant Ioannis Peroglou at the intersection of Koumpari Street and Vasilissis Sofia Avenue, opposite the National Garden of Athens (Figure 3). In 1895, Panagiotis Harokopos bought it to build the Megaro Harokopos. In 1910, retaining the previous architect Anastasios Metaxas, the building passed to Emmanuel Benakis and was renovated to repatriate his family from Alexandria. Between 1929 and 1931, an extension was made to its western side to serve as a museum. Alekos and Stefanos Kalligas undertook a series of expansions, completed in 1997, which spanned two decades to accommodate the Museum's ever-growing collection. The building, which is under cultural heritage conservation law, was damaged by an earthquake in 1986 and after a \$20,000,000 restoration, it reopened to the public in 2000 in Athens (Sakellaropoulos, 2017).

Figure 3. The main building of the Benaki Museum located in central Athens, Greece

The building has four overground and four underground levels (Figure 4). The underground levels contain storage spaces and electromechanical service rooms, while the overground levels house offices, exhibition rooms, a cafeteria and an amphitheatre. Approximately 17% of the building's total area is dedicated to circulation spaces, including staircases, elevators, and corridors. Table 1 provides an overview of the building's area by function.

Figure 4. Building section of the Benaki Museum building under study. Source: Benaki Museum archives

Table 1. Surface area allocation by use in the Benaki Museum building under study

Use	Area (m ²)	Levels
Storage/electromechanical	974.03	-3, -2, -1
Exhibition spaces	3326.00	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Offices	735.01	0
Library	435.24	0
WC	86.18	-1
Circulation spaces	1147.03	-3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4
Cafeteria	214.86	4
Total area:	6918.35	

2.3 The Benaki Museum Renovation Passport

The EPC for the building was initially prepared using the Greek EPC methodology. A comprehensive audit was conducted, covering the building’s total area (6,918.35 square meters), envelope, and electromechanical systems, to develop an energy model for calculating heating and cooling energy demand loads in compliance with the Greek Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings (KENAK) (Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings, 2017, July 12). The surface area of the facades was derived from the building’s layout and façade plans. U-values, along with the thermal, physical, and technical characteristics of the building’s components and systems, were then entered into the official national EPC calculation software, TEE KENAK (Technical Chamber of Greece, 2024).

The TEE KENAK software employs a range of calculation methods to estimate the energy performance of buildings, based on the methodology of European standards (primarily ISO 13790), relevant national standards, and the Technical Guidelines issued by the Technical Chamber of Greece for the EPC issuing procedure. These methods include heat transfer calculations through building elements such as walls, roofs, and floors, considering the thermal properties of materials. The software also simulates heating and cooling energy demands by incorporating factors such as local climate data, building orientation, and usage patterns. The results are aggregated to determine the building's overall energy efficiency and classify it according to predefined national and European standards. For the Benaki Museum building, the current energy demand was calculated as 318.80 kWh/m² in primary energy and 112.50 kWh/m² in final energy, with CO₂ emissions of 158.57 kg/m². Based on these metrics, the building was classified in Greek energy class Δ.

After issuing the EPC, essential building information—such as the address, total area, use, and current energy class—was manually entered into the iBRoad2EPC Assistant interface (Figure 1). This step initiated the development of a comprehensive stepwise renovation roadmap, tailored to meet the requirements of the managing authorities and Greek legal provisions for public buildings. Meetings with the building's maintenance managers identified immediate priorities for energy upgrades to the envelope and systems. Based on these discussions, the energy inspector who issued the EPC and later collaborated with iBRoad2EPC proposed a series of energy upgrade measures. These measures were organised into three phases, designed to achieve Zero Energy Building status by 2050, aligning with the ambitious European targets for improving the energy efficiency of existing buildings. A detailed overview of the building's current components and systems is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Specification of the building's components and systems before the energy upgrade

	Building component/system	Description and technical or thermal/physical characteristics	Year of construction or last renovation
Envelope	Walls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stone walls with U-values 2.30, 2.00, 1.90 and 1.70 W/m²K according to width (old building) Reinforced concrete and hollow bricks walls with U-value 0.77 W/m²K (1989 wing) 	1930 and 1989
	Roof	Reinforced concrete with expanded polystyrene (XPS) thermal insulation and marble or concrete pavement tiles with U-value 0.65 and 1.15 W/m ² K	1996
	Floors	Concrete floors with U-values 3.10 and 1.15 W/m ² K	1930 and 1989
	Windows/doors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metal or aluminium single-glazed doors/windows with U-values ~ 6.00 W/m²K Wooden double-glazed doors/windows with U-values ~ 3.00 W/m²K Double wooden doors/windows with rolls and U-values ~2.10 W/m²K Wooden triple-glazed windows with U-values ~ 1.40 W/m²K 	1996 and later
HVAC	Heating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 central heat pumps with nominal capacity ~560 kW for heating and cooling with COP=2.4 and EER=2.20 	1996
	Cooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual A/C split units for some offices, the amphitheatre and the cafeteria with COP=~4 and EER=~3.5 	
	Ventilation	4 central Ventilation Units and 2 Fans	1996
	Lighting	Halogen and LED lamps	1996 and later

The measures and technical specifications for their implementation were selected and adapted from the extensive database of measures provided by the iBRoad2EPC Assistant. Key proposed measures included upgrading the lighting equipment and central heat-pump units, insulating the roof, and enhancing the central Building Management System. Table 3 presents the energy upgrade measures proposed for each renovation step, along with the projected year of implementation and the anticipated upgraded energy class of the building after each step.

Table 3. Overview of the proposed energy upgrade measures, allocated to four renovation steps

Step	Year	Proposed Measures	Energy class after renovation
1	ASAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upgrade of lighting 	Δ
2	2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replacement of thermal insulation on the 1989 wing roof • Replacement of old heat pumps with new, energy-efficient ones • Installation of heat recovery units on existent air-conditioning pipes 	B
3	2032	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upgrade of BMS system for monitoring, reporting and automation 	B+
4	2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of Photovoltaic panels on the roof • Upgrade of BMS system to consider grid signals and installation of monitoring sensors for occupancy, IEQ and weather conditions 	A

The Renovation Passport for the Benaki Museum, created using iBRoad2EPC, is an online, dynamic document accessible via a QR code printed on an additional informational page following the building’s standard EPC. Alternatively, it can be printed and delivered directly to the building’s managers by the energy auditor. The passport includes a main page summarizing the critical elements of the renovation strategy, such as the number of steps, proposed implementation years, and an overview of renovated components or systems (Figure 5). Detailed pages accompany each renovation step, providing technical specifications, relevant legal requirements based on national regulations, and notes to prevent lock-in effects. Additionally, supplementary pages offer insights into energy performance, costs, Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), and user influence recommendations, forming a comprehensive energy upgrade roadmap.

Figure 5. The overview page of the renovation strategy for the Benaki Museum as presented into the iBRoad2EPC

iBRoad2EPC incorporates the methodology for Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) calculation (European Commission, 2024, December) and the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) assessment spreadsheet developed by the X-tendo EU-funded project². These aspects are seamlessly integrated into the building's renovation roadmap. For the Benaki Museum building, the methodology only required the SRI to be calculated for each renovation step. The resulting increase in the SRI rating was calculated and included in a dedicated section of the Renovation Passport online document (Figure 6).

Finally, preparation notes for subsequent renovation measures were automatically generated and included in each renovation step by the iBRoad2EPC tool. These notes aim to prevent excessive costs and lock-in effects. They are derived from a predefined set of base and trigger energy upgrade measures, with the option for the energy auditor responsible for certifying the building to freely adapt the text as needed.

² <https://x-tendo.eu>

Figure 6. The SRI rating output page of the renovation strategy for the Benaki museum as presented into the iBRoad2EPC

3. Conclusions

The Benaki Museum, as part of Greece’s legally protected cultural heritage, has presented unique challenges in defining a renovation roadmap toward a zero-emissions building. Restrictions on cultural buildings often make conventional energy upgrade measures impractical or difficult to implement. Nevertheless, this case study demonstrates best practices for applying stepwise energy upgrades in cultural buildings, leveraging Renovation Passports (or enhanced EPCs) to accelerate the transition to a sustainable and efficient European building stock.

A key innovation in this study was the use of the iBRoad2EPC Assistant, which facilitated the creation of a dynamic and adaptable renovation roadmap. Integrating SRI and IEQ assessments into the EPC framework introduced a novel methodology that provides a holistic view of a building’s performance. These advancements improve the accuracy and practical utility of EPCs while setting a precedent for future innovations in building energy performance assessments.

The findings have significant practical implications. For policymakers, integrating Renovation Passport elements into EPCs offers a structured pathway to achieve national and European energy efficiency targets. Building managers gain a clear, step-by-step renovation roadmap to plan and prioritise investments effectively. Furthermore, the incorporation of smart technologies and detailed performance assessments enhances indoor environmental quality for occupants, increasing both the value and the sustainability of buildings.

4. Future work and limitations

While this study provides a comprehensive approach to integrating Renovation Passport elements into EPCs, it has some limitations. The unique characteristics of the Benaki Museum as a cultural heritage building imposes restrictions that may not be applicable to other building types. Future research should explore the application of this methodology to a wider variety of buildings, including residential and commercial properties. Additionally, the long-term effectiveness of the proposed energy upgrade measures should be monitored and evaluated to further refine renovation strategies further. Future studies could also examine the cost-benefit analysis of implementing these measures across different climatic regions and building types.

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The facilitation service for energy renovation of public buildings in Piemonte Region

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Keywords: Energy Performance Contract, Public Buildings, Energy Renovation, Energy Efficiency Investments

1. The importance of energy performance contracting to renovate public buildings

Energy Performance Contracting is a market mechanism through which energy service companies (ESCOs) provide customers with a financially binding guarantee of the energy savings that will be achieved. Although contract models can differ from country to country to meet local needs and ensure success in specific environments (Langlois & Hansen, 2012). EPCs are generally able to address most existing barriers to scaling up of energy efficiency investments in the public sector. These barriers include a lack of technical skills to design appropriate measures, limited financial resources to cover initial costs, and the performance risks associated with large-scale retrofitting investments (Polzin et al., 2016).

The potential for implementing such a mechanism remains largely untapped, though progress has been made in recent years (Langlois & Hansen, 2012). In the European Union, growing trust in Energy Performance Contracting has led to increased adoption, and since 2003, Member States have been required to implement performance-based energy regulations. The recent Directive (EU) 2024/1275 (recast) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings highlights the importance of this financial tool. Specifically, it encourages Member States to promote energy-efficient investments in public buildings through public-private partnerships and energy performance contracts (as defined in Article 2, point (33), of Directive (EU) 2023/1791), aiming to reduce the perceived risk of the investments.

2. The approach followed in Piemonte to upscale energy renovation of public buildings

Promoting energy efficiency investments in public buildings through the use of energy performance contracts as both a technical and financial instrument is considered a valuable strategy for energy saving (Bertoldi et al., 2021).

Public administration must lead by example (EUR-Lex, 2023) and has a dual role under the Directive. First, Member States are responsible for driving the development and implementation of a National Building Renovation Plan. To bring these plans to fruition, effective coordination among national, regional and municipal administrations will be essential. For instance, the network of one-stop-shops will rely on this coordination to enhance public sector efficiency and deliver a unified message to citizens. Second, public administration is also required to improve its own buildings to comply with the Directive, thereby reducing emissions and saving on budget costs (EUR-Lex, 2024). An illustration of this effort is the project GASLESS (Global Assistance Service for Low Energy investments toward a

foSSil free Public sector)¹ (Figure 1), implemented by the Piemonte Region in partnership with Environment Park, PRISMA and SCR Piemonte. This initiative aims to accelerate the transition to a fossil free building stock for public buildings owned by regional authorities.

Figure 1. Example of good practice: Riqualificazione energetica STEPPING plus

Since Energy Performance Contracts are complex, a Project Development Assistance service (PDA) service to support small and medium municipalities is essential if they contracts are to be implemented (Bleyle-Androschin & Schinnerl, 2009). This PDA should be a one-stop shop approach, offering comprehensive assistance and solutions throughout the entire investment chain –from the decision making process to performance monitoring.

Upscaling the energy renovation rate of public buildings, accelerating the shift from natural gas to renewables, and reducing public budget expenditures are key challenges the Piemonte Region faces in its pursuit of long-term carbon neutrality. There are also significant opportunities, such as access to various financial schemes that support decarbonization efforts and widespread political consent for energy transition policies. To achieve the Green Deal objectives, the regional administration must play a strong role in coordinating and supporting local authorities, which often lack the necessary skills and resources.

3. The service provided by the Gasless project

Based on successful European projects such as 2020Together (Città metropolitana di Torino, 2015), Stepping and Stepping Plus –which facilitated over €20 million in sustainable energy investments through Energy Performance Contracts–Piemonte Region is now establishing a facilitation service for deep renovation of public buildings. This one-stop shop service, designed for public organizations across the region (Boza-Kiss & Bertoldi, 2018; Bertoldi et al., 2021) offers comprehensive technical, financial and legal support, including procurement management and quality assurance. It is to be self-sustainable in the future.

Developed under the GASLESS project, funded by the European Commission, this service aims to support multiple public institutions in refurbishing approximately 100 public buildings over the next

¹ <https://www.sportelloenergia.envipark.com/edifici-pubblici-en/>

four years. Between 2024 and 2026, five joint procurement procedures will be launched, with an expected total investment of around €50 million.

The project partners—Piemonte Region, Environment Park, PRISMA, and SCR Piemonte—bring together all the necessary expertise, covering administrative, technical, financial, procurement, and legal aspects.

The project takes an innovative approach to activating building renovation investments by addressing several key barriers, including:

- **Market fragmentation:** By bringing together small municipalities, the project fosters collaboration to achieve greater impacts.
- **Lack of skills:** It helps overcome the challenge of managing complex administrative and financial procedures, such as Public-Private Partnership schemes.
- **Access to finance:** The financial model transfers the financial risk to Energy Service Companies (ESCOs), making it easier for the public sector to engage in energy renovation projects.

A series of case studies of past energy efficiency investments achieved through Energy Performance Contracts in Piemonte and the facilitation structure established by the Region have been carried out under the GASLESS project. These investments are organised using a bundling approach, involving multiple municipalities selected through an open call for interest, aimed at creating economies of scale and bankable projects. This project is a complex administrative challenge that requires a great deal of coordination and effort on behalf of the organisers. However, this resulted in the signing of binding agreements among the beneficiaries of the project development assistance service that includes energy audits, financial assessments of various solutions, tendering procedures, and general legal support.

The financial solution adopted aligns with a public-private partnership model, where the awarded company ESCO assumes the financial, operational, and performance risks. Public authorities will not cover upfront costs but will instead pay a fee over time, based on the ordinary energy costs already incurred before the renovation works. The fee will be paid in full only if the ESCO meets the guaranteed energy performance targets.

The project does not provide additional funding but ensures that available funds are utilised in an innovative and effective manner. Upfront investment costs are covered through equity from the ESCO, national and regional incentives, and the savings generated during the implementation of the contracts. In Italy, the "conto termico" programme currently covers up to 65% of energy efficiency investments for public buildings, and it integrates well with the EPC mechanism. In this context, the ESCO assumes the financial risk and, as a public administration, is entitled to claim the incentives.

Past experiences demonstrate that such investment projects are valuable and impactful (Boza-Kiss & Bertoldi, 2018), shifting the focus from the construction works to the results they deliver: energy savings, renewable energy production, and CO₂ emission reductions. The results, measured over several years and following international standards (Efficiency Valuation Organization, n.d.) will be provided, highlighting the achieved impacts.

The GASLESS project is currently in its first phase of implementation. At the moment, 27 buildings from ten public organizations are already under assessment, with plans to tender these projects before the end of the year.

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Spanish e-building logbook: Theoretical structure based on stakeholders' views.

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1. Introduction

In April 2024, the recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (EU 2024/1275) was approved by the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union (2024). This update aims to enhance carbon emission provisions for new buildings and introduces minimum energy performance standards for existing non-residential buildings.

The adaptation of the EPBD provides an impetus for the progressive –and mandatory– renovation of Europe's building stock. To ensure its success, the Directive requires robust national building renovation plans and additional provisions for decarbonising heating and cooling systems (Sibileau & Vladyka, 2024). The EPBD introduces three areas of particular relevance to this work: 1) Valorisation of the Renovation Passport (RP), as a tool to provide a clear trajectory for phased deep renovations proposed to be voluntarily adopted by Member States by 29 May 2026; 2) Promotion of one-stop shops to provide information, advice and financial support for energy renovations; and 3) National Trajectories (NT) as the primary regulatory instrument to trigger large-scale renovations of existing residential buildings.

In specialised literature, the analysis and development of a RP is often embedded in a much larger data framework known as the Digital Building Logbook (DBL). This comprehensive data scheme integrates the RP alongside information from Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) and new indicators such as the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) or the Global Warming Potential (GWP). In turn, a representation of the Scheduled Renovation Roadmap (SRR), should be included in the structure of the RP, encompassing: 1) the technology, technique and material options to be used, 2) the estimated energy savings in primary and final energy consumption compared to the previous phase, 3) the expected reduction of operational GHG emissions, 3) the expected savings in energy bills, 4) the expected energy class in the EPC to be achieved after the end of the renovation phase.

It goes without saying that a tool like the RP cannot function as an isolated information scheme. It must operate within an interconnected feedback loop to ensure the seamless integration of data. This is particularly critical for the development of a Spanish RP, where the challenge lies not in the absence of building information management tools but in their independent operation, namely: the Building Logbook (for new buildings) (LdE), the Existing Building Logbook (LEdEx), the Certificate of Habitability (CdH), the Technical Building Inspection Report (IITE) and the EPC. Maintaining these tools in isolation could hinder the development of an effective RP. The disconnected application of these components risks creating data interconnection issues in the medium to long term. Such fragmentation could reduce the value of the data and undermine stakeholder interest in relying on accurate, secure, and sustainable building information (Lützkendorf, 2011; Lützkendorf & Lorenz, 2011; Miller & Lützkendorf, 2016).

In light of this situation, it is urgent for Spain to develop a tool capable of managing the vast amount of building and housing data—both conventional and energy-related—across their entire life cycle. Such a tool must address the diverse information requirements of various types of buildings and

dwellings. Beyond facilitating the energy rehabilitation of housing to meet the established NT, the tool should aim to achieve energy efficiencies comparable to near-zero energy consumption by 2050. This is particularly critical given that more than half of Spain's housing stock was built before 1980, and has therefore suffered significant ageing. These older buildings represent 30.1% of total final energy consumption and contribute to 25.1% of carbon emissions (Bellver et al., 2021).

Therefore, this study proposes the development of a theoretical framework for an instrument termed the e-Building Logbook (LdE-e). This tool is informed by the opinions of a panel of experts in the sustainable real estate market and consolidates the data scheme envisioned by the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: the objectives and methodology are discussed in Section 2, followed by the presentation of results in Section 3, and the conclusions in Section 4.

2. Objective and methodology

Given the intricate nature of a tool like this, obtaining feedback from stakeholders at each phase of its development is crucial. This study takes a significant step forward in the development of the DBL+RP for Spain, which we have named the LdE-e, through the systematic interviewing of a panel of experts specializing in energy efficiency and green finance.

The initial phase involved an extensive literature review, covering both the RP and existing building management instruments in Spain (Espinoza-Zambrano & Marmolejo-Duarte, 2022). This review was further enriched by studies conducted by the European Commission on the maturity of DBL frameworks across Europe (Carbonari et al., 2020) and on the technical guidelines for DBL operationalisation within an European context (Ecorys et al., 2022). Building on these foundations, a prototype structure for the LdE-e was developed and subsequently presented in theory to the panel of experts during the second phase.

Specifically, the research methodology for the second phase is developed in the following steps:

1. **DBL+RP prototyping.** Based on the reviewed literature and data from building information management tools in Spain, an initial prototype of the tool was created. This process also considered the technological integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM)—to facilitate accurate access to physical and technical building data—and Blockchain technology, aimed at ensuring traceability, transparency, and security of information throughout the building's life cycle.
2. **Identification of the Panel of Experts.** It is comprised of specialists in energy efficiency, real estate developers, property agents, property managers, and representatives from the administration, all with a vested interest in energy-efficient building practices (Table 1).

Table 1. Panel of experts interviewed

Industry	Institution – Organization – Company	Experts	Background Code
Technical professionals	Self-employed	4	TE
Technicians' associations	Association of Quantity Surveyors, Technical Architects and Building Engineers of Barcelona (CATEB) Architecture and Sustainability (AuS)	2	CP
Real estate professionals	Association of Developers and Constructors of Catalonia (APCE) Barcelona Association of Real Estate Agents (API) Association of Property Managers of Barcelona-Lleida (CAFBL)	5	PI
Government	Housing Agency of Catalonia (AHC) Local Energy Agency of Barcelona (Barcelona City Council)	2	AD

3. **Approach to and undertaking of interviews.** The interviews were semi-structured, enabling experts to elaborate on areas where they had greater knowledge, divided into the following thematic blocks:

- Unified information registry
- Data recording per housing unit
- New and Existing LdE-e
- Governance
- Management
- Utility or barriers of ICT associated with LdE-e (BIM methodology and Blockchain technology)
- The role of one-stop shops in SRR
- Data usage policies
- Barriers to LdE-e adoption
- Tool implementation requirements/costs

The interviews were conducted online with an average duration of 40 minutes. Experts were provided with a general overview of the project before the interview, allowing them to prepare their insights in advance.

4. **Analysis of the interviews, validation, or reformulation of the LdE-e proposal.** Each expert's responses were transcribed from the audio recordings and they were organised into a table based on the thematic blocks. While the names of the expert panel members are available, their individual responses have been anonymised and are presented using acronym codes throughout the text. The most relevant insights are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Summary of opinions by interview block

Analysis blocks	Expert panel's opinions
Unified information registry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Positive consensus on the initial hypothesis of this work on the unification of the existing technical documents (CdH, EPC; IITE), as their separate scope is not the same. – The experts (PI) pointed out the usefulness of a unified register to consider all possible incidents that have affected a building prior to a real estate transaction. – The need to digitalise the LdE-e and to enter and retrieve information interactively (CP). – On the Administration side (AD), LEdEx already functions as a unified EPC+IITE register but it is not a digital tool, which impedes dynamic data flows. – Several experts (AD, CP) pointed out that it is crucial to analyse the quality and accuracy of the information to be integrated in the LdE-e register, especially for the understanding of non-technical people.
Data recording per housing unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Positive consensus on the importance of having complete information on a building and on each of the dwellings that compose it (AD). – However, the lack of rigour in data entry and the fact that existing tools are only designed to comply with administrative records (CP) were pointed out.
New and Existing LdE-e	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The experts (CP) stressed the need for a single data structure that can be interoperable and shared with stakeholders specialised in sustainable construction. – In other words, the LdE-e should be a tool that can provide data for housing policy making, not just a data repository (AD).
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The governance of the LdE-e was perceived as complex, especially as there are many stakeholders. – Some experts suggested a more technical vision of the LdE-e, where the tool should be hosted on a public portal and preferably governed by a specific entity (DP). – It was suggested that each of the registry's modules or data packages should be developed by specific technical associations based on their technical expertise (AD).
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – In this block there were divergent opinions. – Some experts argued that due to the complexity of the LdE-e, it should be managed by a technical professional and not by the owners (TE). – Others felt that the role of the technical professional already lies with the property managers (TE, PI). – Other experts believed that the figure of the “primary technician” should be promoted (AD). – Consensus on the non-management by third parties, although permissions should be granted for access to data. – General distrust about possible illegal sale of data.
Utility or barriers of ICT associated with LdE-e (BIM methodology and Blockchain technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Despite the lack of full agreement among experts, there was a widespread view that technologies such as BIM and blockchain could be of great use due to their organisational capabilities and data mining possibilities. – Some experts argued that a digital twin could provide insight into hidden defects in a building or a house (TE, CP).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Blockchain is adopted with caution. It is argued that the veracity/accuracy of data should be provided by technicians and not by technology (AD). – Doubts arose about the difficulty of implementing blockchain in the LdE-e, as the technological training of technicians entails logistical and economic efforts that could delay its implementation.
The role of one-stop shops in SRR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The experts (TE) consider that the recently created Technical Rehabilitation Offices (OTR) can help owners' associations to identify the rehabilitation roadmap included in the LdE-e. – Opinions were divided on the role of the OSS. Some experts suggested that all architects involved in building renovation already do the job of encouraging users to renovate, and that the implementation of OSS may be good but not effective, because owners will always choose the cheapest option (TE). – Other experts were clearly in favour of the implementation of OSS (AD), as these entities inform owners about existing efficiency subsidies linked to NextGeneration funds.
Data usage policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The experts agreed that a housing stock data set would benefit government policies (AD). However, they raised concerns about open data publicity, stressing the need to protect confidential information (CP, TE, AD, PI).
Barriers to LdE-e adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Energy efficiency is not a key factor in buying, renting, or renovating a house, according to all experts (TE, AD, CP, PI). – Although awareness has improved compared to a few years ago, there is still a strong need to raise awareness about energy retrofits (AD). – The rise in electricity and gas prices could be a chance to highlight the potential of tools like the LdE-e (AD). – Information campaigns on Next Generation EU subsidies are starting to shift people's mentality (CP). – Despite increased awareness, the high upfront cost of energy retrofits remains a major barrier, especially for low-income neighbourhoods (PI)
Tool implementation requirements/costs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Experts lacked a clear idea of the theoretical cost of developing the LdE-e. – Some (TE) referred to existing BRPs in the EU, but these costs aren't comparable to Spain's economy. – Others (CP) suggested it might be like the cost of LEED or BREEAM certification, though they were not fully convinced.

3. Results

The findings of this research have been extensively detailed in a previous scientific article (Espinoza-Zambrano et al., 2023). A summary of the key results obtained is presented below.

Figure 1. Structure of LdE-e (new building) validated by experts. Own elaboration

Based on the prototype structure of the LdE-e, experts generally agreed on the need to create distinct structures for new and existing buildings, as their information requirements differ significantly. A unified structure could lead to confusion. The proposed package-based structure was well-received, though some experts representing property management administration suggested incorporating additional data packages in the future. These could include financial variables or indicators tracking property valuation over time, such as the new Global Warming Potential (GWP) or Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), as renovations progress.

Regarding governance and management, experts proposed two potential approaches: supervision by independent organizations or by an entity uniting various administrative bodies focused on sustainable building practices. The latter suggestion stems from a shared desire to accelerate energy renovation efforts in Spain, which have been hindered by excessive bureaucracy and the challenges of both vertical and horizontal administrative fragmentation..

Figure 1 illustrates the general structure of the LdE-e, as validated by the experts for new buildings. The structure is divided into three main sections:

1. **Document Repository (DR)**, with the data assets of the existing documents along with a supporting file package referred to as the Warehouse, which stores all files that substantiate the data.

2. **Interconnected Data Structure (IDS)**, with a structure five interrelated packages: Technical/formal data, Legal data, Identification of deficiencies; One-off actions, Maintenance and repair scheduling.
3. **Scheduled Renovations Roadmap (SRR)** throughout the life cycle of the building allowing it to update existing certificates—such as the Certificate of Habitability (CdH), Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), and Technical Building Inspection Report (IITE)—as required or mandated.

Given the complexity of the SRR, stemming from the dynamic nature of the information and the involvement of multiple stakeholders, Figure 2 provides a detailed implementation structure. This structure identifies four main actors:

1. **Owners/users**, as the primary stakeholders for initiating and carrying out the phased renovation process
2. **OSS**, serving as the support scheme for all involved parties
3. **Primary technician**, whose control and management role is outlined in the ERESEE Strategy (Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana, 2020)
4. **Installer or Construction Company**, which executes the actions proposed by the primary technician and validated by all parties.

Figure 2. Structure of the Scheduled Renovation Roadmap

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) remains a complex issue, primarily due to the training required for technicians. Nonetheless, it is viewed as a critical requirement, particularly as the EPBD emphasised the transition to smart buildings. Regarding the BIM methodology, experts recognise its potential to facilitate the transfer of information to the LdE-e using standards such as the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). However, they noted that this utility is currently only feasible for new buildings where BIM is integrated from the design phase. In the case of Blockchain technology, experts expressed concerns about the complexity of implementing a fully Blockchain-based system. They highlighted the steep learning curve for technicians and the potential for it to hinder the tool's rollout. As a result, the Blockchain proposal was refined to a tokenization gateway. This simplified approach can validate the latest versions of key documents, such as the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), Certificate of Habitability (CdH), or Technical Building Inspection Report (IITE).

4. Conclusion

The latest recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) mandates that member states introduce a voluntary Renovation Passport (RP) scheme by 29 May 2026. This study, through semi-structured interviews with experts, aims to develop a consolidated data structure integrating all building information into a unified database. Expert feedback, including insights beyond the regional level, has validated the theoretical structure of the e-Building Logbook (LdE-e), setting the stage for its practical implementation via prototypes for both new and existing buildings.

A theoretical RP structure tailored for Spain has been developed, integrating the DBL and RP into a single interconnected digital database. This structure utilises dynamic data packages which are updated each time a Scheduled Renovations Roadmap (SRR) stage is completed during the building's lifecycle. Updates also occur when specific Spanish building information management documents—such as CdH, IITE, or EPC—require revision, or when renovation activities require modifications to building-related data.

It is important to highlight that while the LdE-e framework is based on a common European structure (Carbonari et al., 2020), the origin and interconnection of datasets are adapted to Spain's unique legislative context, as each EU Member State operates under different regulations for building information management tools. Typically, the development of a BRP typically begins with consolidating existing information, and this research could serve as a reference point for initial efforts preceding BRP implementation.

Future research on this topic will focus on three key areas before moving toward real-case implementation:

- **Expanding the Scope of Expert Opinions:** Extending the research to a national level, as the current panel has primarily represented the regional context of Catalonia.
- **Engaging Key Stakeholders:** Gathering insights from crucial actors in the renovation process, particularly building owners and users.
- **Exploring BIM Integration:** Investigating the technical and operational synergies between Building Information Modelling (BIM) and the LdE-e to maximise potential advantages.

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